

Comparison of vocal repertoires of
beluga whales (*Delphinapterus leucas*)
in the eastern Chukchi and Beaufort Seas

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I hereby certify that this dissertation, which is approximately 11,628 words in length, has been composed by me, that it is the record of work carried out by me and that it has not been submitted in any previous application for a degree. This project was conducted by me at the University of St. Andrews from January 2024 to August 2024 towards fulfilment of the requirements of the University of St Andrews for the degree of Master of Science of Marine Mammal Science under the supervision of Dr. Ellen Garland and Dr. Julie Oswald.

18/08/2024 Amanda C Rohr

Table of Contents

Abstract	1
Acknowledgements	2
I. Introduction	3
Beluga whale vocal repertoire	5
Beluga whales in Alaska	6
Present study	8
II. Methods:	8
A. Study area and data collection	8
B. Data analysis	10
1. Selection of recordings	10
2. Spectrographic analysis	10
3. Manual classification of call types	11
4. Quantitative classification of call types	13
5. Repertoire comparison.....	16
III. Results:	17
A. Manual classification of call types	17
1. Whistles	18
2. Pulsed calls, noisy calls, and clicks	20
3. Combined calls	21
B. Quantitative classification of call types	22
C. Repertoire comparison	23
IV: Discussion	26
References:	33
Appendix 1:	41
Appendix 2:	53

ABSTRACT

Consistent variation in vocalizations between populations has been used to acoustically identify many cryptic species to a population level. Beluga whales (*Delphinapterus leucas*) are a strong candidate for having population-specific vocal repertoires due to their diverse, complex set of vocalizations and sociable nature. The present study explored this with the genetically-distinct eastern Chukchi Sea (ECS) and eastern Beaufort Sea (BS) beluga populations that share an annual seasonal migration route between Arctic and sub-Arctic seas. The BS beluga vocal repertoire has already been described, so first this study described the ECS beluga vocal repertoire and then quantitatively compared the vocal repertoires of both populations. Across 11 days of recordings, 751 ECS beluga calls were measured on thirteen variables and subjectively categorized into 46 call types. The Random Forest classifier showed 78.8% agreement with the manual classification. The discovery curve was still increasing, indicating that an incomplete vocal repertoire was captured here for the ECS belugas. For the comparison of their vocal repertoires, 750 calls from each population were used to train a Random Forest classifier, which correctly assigned each call to its true population 78.0% of the time. When exploring only whistles, the Random Forest accurately classified 79.5% of whistles to its population. Both Random Forest classifiers determined the most useful variables for differentiating between populations were frequency trend, duration, and bandwidth. These findings show that the ECS and BS belugas can be recognized by the population-specific characteristics in their vocal repertoires. Given that the ECS belugas number close to one-third of the BS beluga population, this information has wide implications for their respective population management and conservation efforts. With an increasing presence of oil, gas, and commercial shipping in the Arctic, these findings could be beneficial for better monitoring of the belugas and assessing the impacts of the anthropogenic activities.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Using acoustic signals to relay information between individuals (i.e., a signaler and a receiver) is how many species effectively navigate social situations (Janik and Slater, 2000; Oswald, et al., 2022; Sainberg, Thielk and Gentner, 2020). An animal's location, context (e.g., predator approaching), identity, social status, or group membership can be transmitted through vocal signaling (Barker, et al., 2021; Janik and Slater, 2000; Oswald, et al., 2007; Sainberg, Thielk and Gentner, 2020). Distinct vocalizations can also convey specific social affiliations or belonging to a certain geographic region within a population (Hersh, et al., 2022; Balcazar, et al., 2015). Within bird species, Little Hermits hummingbirds (*Phaethornis longuemareus*) have 'song neighborhoods' (Wiley, 1971); whereas mountain white-crowned sparrows (*Zonotrichia leucophrys*) have firmer discrete 'song dialects' proven to influence gene flow and population structure (MacDougall-Shackleton and MacDougall-Shackleton, 2001). Among terrestrial mammals, vocal dialects in naked mole-rats (*Heterocephalus glaber*; Barker, et al., 2021) and greater sac-winged bats (*Saccopteryx bilineata*; Knörnschild, et al., 2012) have been shown to indicate colony identity. For marine mammals, examples include bearded seals (*Erignathus barbatus*), whose vocalizations vary according to geographic distribution (Charrier, Mathevon and Aubin, 2013; Risch, et al., 2007), and sperm whales (*Physeter macrocephalus*) in the Galápagos Islands that identify with a unique vocal clan, each having a different dialect despite spatially overlapping ranges (Hersh, et al., 2022). These variations in acoustic signals between populations are extremely valuable for tracking cryptic species and identifying nearby sympatric populations, which can help guide their respective conservation management (Balcazar, et al., 2015; Rankin, et al., 2016; Sharpe, et al., 2019).

Variability in a species' vocal repertoire is hypothesized to develop with a greater likelihood in those navigating dynamic social networks and environments, where a need arises for a complex communication system (i.e., high diversity in function and structure of their acoustic signals) (Freeburg, Dunbar and Ord, 2012). In a marine habitat where sound travels almost 4.5 times faster than on land (Lammers and Oswald, 2015), examples of population-specific vocal repertoires have emerged from social toothed whales (odontocetes) with some navigating fission-fusion societies (Connor, et al., 2000; Hawkins, 2010; Bazúa-Durán and Au, 2004), and others a close-knit matrilineal society (Filatova, et al., 2012; Van Cise, et al., 2018; Gero, Whitehead and Rendell, 2016). For example, Indo-pacific bottlenose dolphins (*Tursiops aduncus*) (Hawkins, 2010; Morisaka, et al., 2005) and Hawaiian spinner

dolphins (*Stenella longirostris*) (Bazúa-Durán and Au, 2004) engage in multifaceted social interactions with fluid group formations, and within each species, population identity has been determined from the geographic variability in their vocalizations. In the matrilineally-driven societies of short-finned pilot whales (*Globicephala macrorhynchus*; Van Cise, et al., 2018) or resident killer whales from the north Pacific Ocean (*Orcinus orca*; Ford, 1991), they have developed specific vocal dialects within sympatric subgroups, reflecting their social affiliations. The nested social hierarchy of the resident killer whales is illustrated through their particular vocal repertoires as individuals can be identified from their larger vocal clan down to their specific matrilineal pod (Ford, 1991). These examples of vocal complexity in toothed whales highlight the importance of investigating vocal repertoires, as they can shed light on genetic and culturally driven subdivisions within social systems, ultimately providing insight into population structure.

To gain this level of understanding, consistent classification schemes and analytical methods are needed to successfully compare the vocal repertoires of different populations and subpopulations within a species (Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b; Risch, et al., 2007). In a process that inherently involves individual interpretation, common methodology begins with an observer manually classifying calls into distinct call types using structural features and aural qualities of the call in the spectrogram (Sharpe, et al., 2019). To quantitatively assess population identity, Random Forests (Breiman, 2001) have been used as a robust, nonparametric statistical approach (e.g., Sharpe, et al., 2019). A Random Forest comprises an assemblage of unique decision trees, or a ‘forest’, each ‘voting’ for a population. These decision trees are trained on quantitative call measurements and the final ‘vote’ is the majority decision of the trees (Breiman, 2001; Strobl, Malley and Tutz, 2009). Random Forest analysis can handle missing values and a large number of predictor variables, and the results are easy to interpret with output indicating the most important variables for the model’s classification (Strobl, Malley and Tutz, 2009). In contrast, statistical approaches such as Discriminant Function Analysis or clustering analysis require normally distributed data, have difficulty with highly correlated frequency measurements, and struggle with high-dimensional data (Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b; Karlsen, et al., 2002). Random Forests have been implemented to quantitatively assess population identity based on the vocal repertoires of various odontocetes, including killer whales (*Orcinus orca*; Sharpe, et al., 2019) and pantropical spotted dolphins (*Stenella attenuata*; Rege-Colt et al., 2023).

Taken together, the evidence of population identity encoded in the vocal repertoires of some of the sociable toothed whales calls attention to what other toothed whales possibly have population-specific vocal repertoires. The beluga whale is a prime candidate based on their vocally complex repertoire and gregarious nature (Brewer, et al., 2023; O’Corry-Crowe, et al., 2020; Angiel, 1997).

Beluga whale vocal repertoire

Belugas are ice-associated toothed whales with a circumpolar distribution, inhabiting offshore and coastal areas of the Arctic and sub-Arctic waters (Chmelnitsky and Ferguson, 2012; Young, et al., 2023). Early sailors coined these whales as the “canaries of the sea” after hearing their calls through the ship’s hull (Karlsen, et al., 2002; O’Corry-Crowe, 2009). Previous work has noted some of their vocalizations as “chirps”, “squeals”, “honks” and “screams” (Chmelnitsky and Ferguson, 2012; Sjare and Smith, 1986b). Faucher provided illustrative descriptors of “squirrel”, “chainsaw”, and a “drum stick hitting a cymbal” for certain call types (1988).

The beluga whales’ highly diverse vocal repertoire can be categorized into whistles, pulsed calls, noisy calls, combined calls, and echolocation clicks (Chmelnitsky and Ferguson, 2012; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b; Karlsen, et al., 2002; Sjare and Smith, 1986b). Whistles are narrowband, tonal sounds, which are subdivided into types depending on the shape or contour of the fundamental frequency (e.g., flat versus modulated) (Sjare and Smith, 1986b). These calls range in frequency from less than 500 Hz to 20 kHz (Chmelnitsky and Ferguson, 2012; Karlsen, et al., 2002). Pulsed calls are a rapid sequence of short, broadband pulses classified based on the repetition of pulses per second. The pulse repetition rate is calculated by examining the difference in frequency between the harmonic intervals (Watkins, 1967). When the harmonic interval cannot be measured to determine the pulse repetition rate, these broadband calls are named noisy calls (Sjare and Smith, 1986b). Combined calls are two calls produced simultaneously or in succession by the same individual. They are considered unique call types and contain both a tonal and pulsed or noisy component (Faucher, 1988). Whistles, pulsed calls, noisy calls, and combined calls are believed to function as communication signals (Faucher, 1988; O’Corry-Crowe, 2009; Sjare and Smith, 1986a). Echolocation clicks are used to navigate and locate prey by emitting a series of individual broadband pulses with a peak frequency of up to 120 kHz (Au, et al.,

1985). Lastly, belugas also produce clicks known as a ‘restricted frequency click series’, which are reported to occur at substantially lower frequencies, up to 7 kHz (Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b; Sjare and Smith, 1986b).

The vocal repertoire of the beluga whale is not comprised of perfectly discrete call types, instead their vocalizations exist on a graded continuum with calls having a general trend in similarity (Chmelnitsky and Ferguson, 2012; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b; Sjare and Smith, 1986b). Belugas have also been documented producing novel sounds that involve mimicry. A well-known example includes a beluga whale manipulating their sound production system (i.e., nasal cavity and phonic lips) to convincingly imitate the cadence and frequency range of human speech (Ridgway, et al., 2012). Their rich vocal repertoire and demonstrated ability of vocal learning prompt the question of whether this vociferous species uses different vocalizations in their repertoires to reference population or individual identity.

Previous work has described the beluga whale vocal repertoires of eight populations globally, including the White Sea, Russia (Belikov and Bel’kovich, 2006, 2007, 2008); Svalbard, Norway (Karlsen, et al., 2002); the St. Lawrence River Estuary, Canada (Faucher, 1988); Churchill River, Hudson Bay, Canada (Chmelnitsky and Ferguson, 2012); Cunningham Inlet, Northwest Territories, Canadian Arctic (Sjare and Smith, 1986b); eastern Beaufort Sea, USA (Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b); Cook Inlet, Alaska, USA (Brewer, et al., 2023); and Bristol Bay, Alaska, USA (Angiel, 1997). Comparisons between populations have been complicated by inconsistent analytical methods and different classification schemes across studies (Chmelnitsky and Ferguson, 2012; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b). Garland, Castellote and Berchok (2015b) were the first to use a Random Forest analysis to assess their subjective classification of the eastern Beaufort Sea beluga whale calls and since then, the same analytical approach has been implemented for the Cook Inlet beluga vocal repertoire (Brewer, et al., 2023). Despite varying statistical approaches over the years, differences in the composition of the vocal repertoires and unique call types in each population have been noted (Brewer, et al., 2023).

Beluga whales in Alaska

Out of the eight beluga whale vocal repertoires studied worldwide, three occur within the Alaskan waters of the United States of America - Bristol Bay (Angiel, 1997), Cook Inlet (Brewer, et al., 2023), and the eastern Beaufort Sea (Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b).

In total, there are five beluga whale populations in Alaska, each named after their summering grounds (O’Corry-Crowe, et al., 1997). The two remaining populations are the Bering Sea and eastern Chukchi Sea beluga whales. Each population is genetically distinct, resulting in their designation as separate management stocks (O’Corry-Crowe, et al., 1997). The Cook Inlet and Bristol Bay beluga whales are resident populations, whereas the Bering Sea, eastern Chukchi Sea, and eastern Beaufort Sea beluga whales are migratory (O’Corry-Crowe, et al., 2018; Young, et al., 2023). The vocal repertoires of the resident populations have been studied (Angiel, 1997; Brewer, et al., 2023) and from the migratory populations, researchers have only described the vocal repertoire of the eastern Beaufort Sea belugas (Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b).

The eastern Beaufort Sea, hereafter the Beaufort Sea (BS), population shares a seasonal migration route with the eastern Chukchi Sea (ECS) belugas (Hauser, et al., 2014). Both populations summer in the Arctic Beaufort Sea and overwinter in the sub-Arctic Bering Sea; however, the timing of their autumn migration differs (Hauser, 2016). In July and August, the BS belugas aggregate in the western Beaufort Sea, above Canada, and by September the BS belugas have already begun their autumn migration, heading east-to-west (Hauser, 2016). As the BS belugas migrate westward in September, the ECS belugas, who spend July and August in the Alaskan Beaufort Sea, travel eastward to areas of dense sea ice in the Canadian Beaufort Sea (Hauser, 2016; Suydam, et al., 2001). The populations temporarily overlap but then switch positions in the Beaufort Sea (Hauser, 2016). By October, the ECS belugas have returned to the Alaskan Beaufort Sea, traveling westward, and the BS belugas have already arrived in the western Chukchi Sea (Hauser, 2016). In November, the BS belugas occupy the southwestern and southern Chukchi Sea, and the ECS belugas aggregate in the eastern Chukchi Sea (Hauser, 2016). As their southern migration continues, the BS and the ECS belugas arrive at the 85-kilometer-wide Bering Strait, which then leads into their respective wintering areas in the sub-Arctic Bering Sea (Citta, et al., 2016; Hauser, et al., 2014; O’Corry-Crowe, et al., 2018). In short, the BS belugas start their autumn migration to overwinter in the Bering Sea earlier than the ECS belugas. The difference in timing is believed to be matrilineally-learned behavior and is also influenced by environmental (e.g., ice formation) factors (Hauser, 2016; O’Corry-Crowe, et al., 2018).

Knowledge about the BS and ECS beluga populations and their migration timing has come from satellite-tagging data, genetic testing, traditional ecological knowledge, and aerial surveys (Citta, et al., 2016; O’Corry-Crowe, et al., 2018; Stafford, et al., 2018; Suydam, 2009). In the latest aerial survey estimates, the BS population numbers close to three times as many

whales as the ECS population. The estimated BS population is 39,258 whales (minimum population of 32,453); however, this outdated estimation was last calculated in 1992 and did not cover their entire summer range (Young, et al., 2023). The estimated ECS population is 13,205 whales (minimum population of 8,875), determined from a 2019 survey (Givens, et al., 2020; Young, et al., 2023). Even with occasional spatial overlap occurring during the peak breeding seasons (i.e., winter and early spring), genetic testing, along with satellite-tagging data, has shown the ECS and BS belugas are distinct subpopulations with limited interbreeding between the two (O’Corry-Crowe, et al., 2018). Whether this genetic separation of the BS and ECS populations is also evident in different dialects or population-specific vocalizations in their particular repertoires is unknown. Addressing this knowledge gap has implications for their respective population management and industry stakeholders (i.e., oil and gas), especially as the presence of the anthropogenic operations continue to advance in the Arctic.

Present study

The present study will be the first to quantitatively compare the vocal repertoires of two beluga whale populations, the ECS and BS belugas. First, the ECS beluga vocal repertoire will be described and quantified, from passive acoustic recordings on their autumn migration route to the Bering Sea. This addresses an important missing piece because the sympatric BS beluga vocal repertoire has already been described and quantified by Garland, Castellote, and Berchok (2015b). Secondly, the present study will then compare the compositions of the ECS and the BS beluga vocal repertoires. The second objective will examine whether the BS and ECS beluga populations can be acoustically identified by their vocal repertoires.

II. METHODS

A. Study area and data collection

Acoustic recordings of beluga vocalizations described and quantified for this study were taken in the northeastern Chukchi Sea, located in the Pacific Arctic waters of Alaska in the United States of America. Data was collected approximately 65 kilometers northwest of Icy Cape, Alaska (Figure 1), by a bottom-mounted passive acoustic mooring, which was deployed from 28 August 2010 to 25 August 2011.

Figure 1. A map of the location of the passive acoustic mooring used in this study, in the context of the Arctic and sub-Arctic seas traveled during the eastern Chukchi Sea and eastern Beaufort Sea belugas’ seasonal migrations.

The long-term, bottom-mounted mooring’s components incorporated an anchor, cable, acoustic release, Autonomous Underwater Recorder for Acoustic Listening (AURAL; Multi-Électronique, Canada) with an HTI-96-min hydrophone (sensitivity of -164 dB re 1 V/ μ Pa and a flat frequency response from 2 Hz to 30 kHz), a built-in temperature sensor, and a sub-surface float. The mooring was situated in a vertical formation at a depth of 43 meters with the hydrophone placed about 6 meters above the seafloor. The acoustic recorder sampled at 16 kHz with a frequency bandwidth of ~ 10 Hz to 8 kHz, a 16 -bit resolution, and operated on a duty cycle of 95 minutes every 300 minutes.

The mooring was initially placed by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) National Marine Fisheries Service (NMFS) to monitor baleen whales, accounting for the low sampling rate of 16 kHz aimed at targeting these animals. The sampled frequency range of 8 kHz is sufficient for this study as it overlaps with the two frequency bands expected to encompass most social calls made by beluga whales (i.e., 1.4 – 3.5 kHz and 2.9 – 7.0 kHz) (Delarue, Laurinolli and Martin, 2011). Echolocation clicks,

however, occur at higher frequencies (i.e., up to 120 kHz) and thus were not recorded due to equipment restrictions (Garland, Berchok and Castellote, 2015a).

B. Data Analysis

1. Selection of recordings

The recordings were selected by carefully considering both the peaks in detections of beluga vocal activity and the migratory timing of populations due to the mooring's placement on the migration route. Garland, Berchok, and Castellote (2015a) examined 291 days' worth of recordings from the northeastern Chukchi Sea mooring, with the first acoustic detection on 10 September 2010 and the final detection during deployment on 27 June 2011. Two strong seasonal peaks in vocal activity in the autumn and spring were detected. The spring peaks (i.e., 23 April to 21 May; 18 May to 1 June) correspond to the timing of the BS belugas migrating to their summering grounds in the Beaufort Sea and these recordings were used to describe and quantify the BS beluga vocal repertoire (Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b). The autumn peak in vocal activity (19 to 29 November) on this mooring corresponds to the migratory timing of the ECS belugas heading south toward their Bering Sea wintering grounds (Garland, Berchok and Castellote, 2015a). The BS belugas are not likely to be in the northeastern Chukchi Sea, but rather in the southwestern Chukchi Sea during this autumn peak (Hauser, et al., 2014). Therefore, the autumn peak (i.e., 19 to 29 November) was chosen to ensure the recordings were of ECS beluga whales with no overlap between populations.

2. Spectrographic analysis

The sound files were analyzed using Raven Pro 1.6.5 (Cornell Lab of Ornithology, 2024) smoothed spectrograms, with a 1024-point fast Fourier transform (FFT), Hanning window, 75% overlap, and 23 Hz resolution.

For each day, the data was first visually scanned to determine which sound files contained the highest amount of beluga vocal activity. Then from those predetermined files, calls were annotated starting from files with the highest to lowest abundance of vocal activity. For the days of peak vocal activity (i.e., 23 to 26 November), the overall goal was to annotate around 120 high-quality calls to account for any eliminations that might occur during the quality control phase. Following the methodology of Garland, Castellote, and Berchok (2015b), the first 100 calls from each day during the peak were chosen for analysis. Given that the recordings span over a peak in vocal activity, the days surrounding the peak

had a lower abundance of calls (i.e., less than 100), so in these files every possible high-quality call was annotated. Furthermore, to avoid re-sampling the same migrating pod of ECS belugas, at least one entire duty cycle (i.e., 300 minutes) between high-volume days in the peak was not annotated. In an effort to decrease bias towards high-volume days, a longer buffer was chosen compared to that on low-volume days. Therefore, for low volume days surrounding the peak, at least 3 hours was chosen as a sufficient buffer between different ECS beluga pods. Based on an average beluga swim speed of 3 km hr⁻¹ (Goetz, et al., 2012), the migrating belugas would likely have traveled out of the area within that time.

The high-quality calls selected for this analysis had to meet the criteria of a signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of greater than 10 dB above background noise levels (Brewer, et al., 2023; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b). For each annotated call, SNR was automatically measured by Raven Pro 1.6.5 as SNR NIST Quick (Cornell Lab of Ornithology, 2024). Adapted from Chmelnitsky and Ferguson's (2012) approach and incorporating the SNR NIST Quick values, only the calls that met this criterion were subsequently graded on a scale of 1 (excellent) to 3 (average). Calls with a grade of 1 (excellent) scored above 20 dB SNR, a grade of 2 (good) scored between 15 and 20 dB SNR, and a grade of 3 (average) scored between 10 and 15 dB SNR. Furthermore, calls were selected only if the call was not overlapping in frequency and time with any other sound and if it was the only sound in the selection box. Together, all of the above measures were implemented so that a variety of quality calls from different ECS beluga pods were included in the analysis.

3. Manual classification of call types

Following the classification scheme established by Sjare and Smith (1986b) and updated by Garland, Castellote, and Berchok (2015b), calls were classified visually and aurally, matching them to call types. Calls were first sorted by vocalization family into one of five categories: (1) whistle, (2) pulsed, (3) noisy, (4) combined, or (5) click. Within each vocalization family, calls were grouped by contour shape (e.g., flat, modulated, n-shaped) and further subdivided by the call's structure (e.g., segmented). Taken together, the calls were then placed into a call type (e.g., modulated segmented whistle). The naming system in this study is from Garland, Castellote, and Berchok (2015b), where a shorthand nomenclature is used to represent all of these aspects of a call type (Appendix 1, Table A). For example, a modulated segmented whistle is notated as a modws.seg. Specifically, for n-shaped whistles (nws) and u-shaped whistles (uws), further abbreviations are added to illustrate the number of segments in the call's structure (e.g., nws.seg.b has two segments). Either a step in frequency

(i.e., no time elapsed) or a break in time (i.e., a gap in time greater than 0.02 seconds) is counted as a segment in a single, broken call.

To decide whether a call was separate from another or one part of a broken (segmented) singular call, the calls separated by more than 0.2 seconds were considered separate and those separated by less than 0.2 seconds were treated as segments of a single call. For whistles, this decision was determined by examining the fundamental frequency, and for pulsed calls, it was based on examining the lowest frequency contour. For a new call type or new subdivision of a call type in the whistle or pulsed vocalization family to be established, the call type needed to be observed at least three times (Appendix 1, Table B). These two rules are adopted from previous beluga vocal repertoire studies, aimed at increasing the likelihood that the classified call types are from calls of a single animal versus an unknown number of animals vocalizing over each other (Brewer, et al., 2023; Chmelnitsky and Ferguson, 2012; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b).

In this study, two subdivisions were added to the nomenclature under the whistle vocalization family. A subdivision was created for a specific segmented modulated whistle (modws.seg), with a unique whistle contour of a descending slope, most of which ended in an inflection point (i.e., > 100 Hz; Appendix 1, Table B), and then a step in frequency with a final descending component of the call (Appendix 1, Figure A). This whistle was observed in repetition in various sound files and thus was given a descriptor of “.b” (i.e., modws.seg.b), following Sjare and Smith’s (1986b) naming system. The second subdivision was created for a distinct n-shaped whistle (nws), whose waveform displayed pulsed components (i.e., amplitude modulation) in the signal (Murray, Mercado and Roitblat, 1998). As a result, it was determined to be pulsed and therefore, given the descriptor of “.pul” (i.e., nws.pul). The pulsed whistle (or “pistle”) was also seen in repetitive sequences (Appendix 1, Figure A).

Under the vocalization family of the pulsed call, three new contours and one new subdivision were added to the naming system of Garland, Castellote, and Berchok (2015b). Distinct r-shaped pulsed calls were observed, mimicking the unique contour of the r-shaped whistle, and named “pulse.R” (Appendix 1, Figure B). As also noted in Brewer et al.’s (2023) naming scheme, a pulsed call with a n-shaped contour was given the descriptor of “.n”; however, in this study, the descriptor was added to the existing subdivision of pulsed calls based on pulse-repetition rate (e.g., pulse.I.n). Further expanding upon this nomenclature, pulsed calls with a u-shaped contour (i.e., descending then ascending) were denoted by adding a “.u” to the end of the call type name (e.g., pulse.A.u) (Appendix 1, Table A, Figure B). The naming of these additional pulsed contours drew inspiration from the r-shaped, n-

shaped, and u-shaped contours already recognized in the whistle vocalization family. To describe a segmented pulsed call, a descriptor of “.seg” was added to the end of the call type name (e.g., pulse.I.seg) adapted from the nomenclature in the Cook Inlet beluga vocal repertoire (Brewer, et al., 2023). This is the same descriptor used to describe other whistle call types with a segmented structure.

To assess whether the beluga calls described in these acoustic recordings reflect a complete ECS beluga vocal repertoire, a discovery curve was constructed in RStudio (Posit Team, 2023) using R (R Core Team, 2023) by first randomly ordering the calls and then plotting the number of unique call types against the number of calls (i.e., sample size). The plotted curve increases with each newly added call type and when there are no new call types, the discovery curve becomes asymptotic (Brewer, et al., 2023). If the discovery curve depicts an asymptote, then the classified calls have captured an almost complete vocal repertoire (Brewer, et al., 2023). Given the curve’s shape is determined by the order in which the new call types are plotted, the shape of the discovery curve is dependent on where a new call type is positioned in the randomized dataset. This process was therefore repeated for 200 different randomized iterations and plotted on a single discovery curve. R packages *dplyr* and *viridis* were used to assist with data manipulation and the plotted color gradient for the randomized iterations on the discovery curve (Garnier, et al., 2024; Wickham, et al., 2023).

4. Quantitative classification of call types

In Raven Pro 1.6.5 (Cornell Lab of Ornithology, 2024), beluga whistles chosen for analysis were isolated by placing a selection box tightly around the fundamental frequency of the whistle. For noisy and pulsed calls, the entire broadband signal was included inside the selection box. Combined calls were boxed three times: once for the whistle component, once for the pulsed component, and once for the overall call to calculate the entire call’s duration. Calls were chosen only if there were no other sounds inside the selection box.

Raven Pro 1.6.5 (Cornell Lab of Ornithology, 2024) automatically generated sound measurements, including duration (s), minimum and maximum frequency (Hz), bandwidth (Hz) (i.e., delta frequency), peak frequency (Hz), and the SNR NIST Quick (dB), a measure of signal-to-noise ratio. Manual measurements of each selected sound included the start and end frequency (Hz) of the fundamental (for whistles), the number of inflection points, breaks, and steps, and the pulse repetition rate (PRR) (for pulsed calls). Two additional variables, frequency trend (Hz) and frequency range (Hz), were calculated based on manual measurements (Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b) (Table 1). In this study, a call with a

“terminal tail” was defined as a call with a final slope (i.e., tail), in a singular direction after a previous change in slope, measuring as fifty percent or more of the call’s structure (Appendix 1, Table B). Previous work describing the Cook Inlet beluga vocal repertoire (Brewer, et al., 2023), only notated “terminal tail” for certain call types and added a descriptor of “.t” to these call types. Here, however, the rule for terminal tail was defined and applied to every call type except flat whistles and mostly flat whistles, but the descriptor of “.t” was not adopted. Instead, qualified calls were only marked with a “terminal tail” comment. Additionally, a call’s vocalization family (e.g., whistle, pulsed) and qualitative name (i.e., call type) were notated when annotating the call.

Table 1. Descriptions of the measurements used for the quantitative classification of the eastern Chukchi Sea beluga call types.

Measurement	Description
Duration (s)	The length of the call in the annotation box. Calculated by the end time (s) subtracting the begin time (s) of the call.
Minimum Frequency (Hz)	The lowest frequency in the call.
Maximum Frequency (Hz)	The highest frequency in the call.
Bandwidth (Hz)	The difference between the minimum frequency and maximum frequency. Also known as the delta frequency.
Peak Frequency (Hz)	The frequency at the peak power (i.e., the darkest and loudest point) occurs within the call.
Start Frequency (Hz)	Start frequency of the fundamental component. Measured using Raven Pro’s cursor positioned at the fundamental’s bottom edge.
End Frequency (Hz)	End frequency of the fundamental component. Measured using Raven Pro’s cursor positioned at the fundamental’s bottom edge.
Frequency Range (Hz)	Ratio of maximum / minimum frequency.
Frequency Trend (Hz)	Ratio of start / end frequency
Inflection Points (#)	A change in modulation (from positive to negative slope or from negative to positive slope) greater than 100 Hz.
Breaks (#)	Number of gaps in time greater than 0.02 seconds in a single, broken (segmented) call.
Steps (#)	Number of frequency gaps without gaps in time.
Pulse Repetition Rate (/s)	Number of pulses per second. Measured using harmonic interval for pulsed and combined calls.

To differentiate between flat whistles (flatws), mostly flat whistles (flatws.m), and ascending or descending whistles, rules were applied based on the bandwidth of each call type found in the whistles' descriptive statistics table in Garland, Castellote, and Berchok (2015b, p. 3059). Flat whistles were those with a bandwidth of 58 - 92 Hz, mostly flat whistles had a bandwidth of 93 - 136 Hz, and whistles with a bandwidth greater than 136 Hz were considered sloped calls (Appendix 1, Table B). For pulsed calls, a selection box was temporarily placed over the loudest frequency contour of the harmonic sound to see whether the call's bandwidth was greater than that of a mostly flat whistle (i.e., > 136 kHz). If so, then the pulsed call was determined to have an ascending or descending contour, and frequency measurements were recorded from the loudest frequency contour. If there was no slope to a pulsed or noisy call, then the start and end frequency were recorded as the peak frequency (Appendix 1, Table B). For combined calls, the pulsed and whistle components were annotated separately and the call's duration was calculated using a third selection box over the entire call, as described in the protocol of Chmelnitsky and Ferguson (2012).

The means and standard deviations of the sound measurements were calculated in R (R Core Team, 2023), using the *psych* package (Revelle, 2024).

Following the methodology used in the BS and Cook Inlet beluga vocal repertoires (Brewer, et al., 2023; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b), a Random Forest analysis with 10,000 trees was used to evaluate the manual classification of call types. For each decision tree in the forest, its 'branches' split at nodes, each split based upon a value of the best predictor variable selected to create new 'branches' that become more uniform with each split (Strobl, Malley and Tutz, 2009). The chosen splitting variable was from a randomly selected subset of predictor variables, making every decision tree in the forest unique. The decision tree kept expanding in this way until it fully developed, achieving the optimal fit for the data. Each decision tree arrived at a call type prediction and the final classification was the call type that received the greatest number of predictions (Breiman, 2001).

To ensure the classifier had no bias to a specific call type, a new dataset was created with an equal number of calls for each call type. The original dataset, including up to the first 100 calls per day, was randomized with a set seed (i.e., 222). Some call type categories appeared only once in the dataset (e.g., pulse.I.u), while others had over sixty calls (e.g., dws) (Tables 2, 3 and 4). Following Garland, Castellote, and Berchok (2015b), some call type categories were combined to create a larger sample size to use in the classifier. The different segmented u-shaped whistles (e.g., uws.seg.c) were combined to create an overall segmented u-shaped whistle call type (i.e., uws.seg). The same approach was also applied to segmented

n-shaped whistles. No other call types were combined. Based on the call type with the lowest sample size, it was decided to use fifteen calls per call type to train the classifier. Call types with fewer than fifteen were not included in training the Random Forest (RF) Model. This number was chosen to be able to include as many call types as possible, though it was an acknowledged tradeoff that limited the balanced dataset's sample size. This resulted in a dataset of 255 calls in seventeen call types.

In addition to the out-of-bag error calculated by the Random Forest analysis, further cross-validation measures were conducted to better estimate the RF Model's performance due to the limited number of calls in each call type category. The balanced dataset was further subdivided into three equal groups (i.e., five calls per call type) to prepare the training and testing datasets for the RF Model. In RStudio (Posit Team, 2023), using R (R Core Team, 2023), the training dataset was assembled by combining two out of the three groups and the third group was used as the testing dataset. This process was repeated so that every group was used in creating both a training and a testing dataset. In every iteration, the decision trees were grown with 10,000 trees and using 170 calls (30 calls per call type). The splitting variable at each node was chosen from three random predictor variables out of thirteen. The RF Model was then tested on 85 calls (15 calls per call type) to determine how it compared to the manual classification of call types.

5. Repertoire comparison

Using a dataset with calls from the ECS and BS beluga populations, a Random Forest classifier was trained to determine whether the populations could be identified based on their vocal repertoires. The classifier was constructed with 10,000 decision trees, each 'voting' on the population (i.e., ECS or BS) based on the quantitative call measurements previously described, except 'number of steps' was excluded as it was not measured for the BS belugas.

To avoid any bias in the classifier, a balanced dataset was created with an equal number of calls from each population. The classification accuracy of the Population RF Model was estimated using the same three-fold cross-validation approach described earlier. A chi-square goodness-of-fit test was performed to examine the results compared to random chance (Social Science Statistics, 2024).

Next, this study explored whether the ECS and BS belugas could be identified to a population-level based on only their whistles. Using the same approach as detailed before, another Random Forest classifier of 10,000 decision trees was created, each placing a 'vote' on which population (i.e., ECS or BS) the whistle originated from. The Whistle-based

Population RF Model was trained using an equal number of whistles from both populations, and three-fold cross-validation was used to determine the accuracy of the classifier. A chi-square goodness-of-fit test was employed to compare the results to random chance (Social Science Statistics, 2024).

Output from every iteration in the RF Model, Population RF Model, and the Whistle-based Population RF Model included the following: a confusion matrix assessing the classifier's performance using out-of-bag error as an internal cross-validation measure, a second confusion matrix evaluating the performance on the test data set (e.g., the remaining group out of three), and both a plot and a list of numerical values of the mean decrease in Gini Index, indicating the significance of each variable in growing the decision trees. The Gini Index values are presented below as an averaged value across all iterations of the three-fold cross-validation, noted as "average mean decrease in Gini Index". The Random Forest analyses were conducted using the R package *randomForest* (Liaw and Wiener, 2002) and the R package *dplyr* was used to help with data manipulation (Wickham, et al., 2023). Analyses were run in RStudio (Posit Team, 2023) using R (R Core Team, 2023).

III. Results

A. Manual classification of call types

The 95 minutes of recordings from each duty cycle were given as ten separate files, with nine recordings of a ten-minute duration and one recording of a five-minute duration. In total over the eleven days of recordings (i.e., 19 to 29 November), there were 531 sound files. For this study, 816 beluga calls were annotated and manually classified. All calls met the requirements for a signal-to-noise ratio above 10 dB. After limiting the dataset to the first 100 calls per day, the final sample size for this study was 751 beluga calls. In total, forty-six call types were identified and these calls were subjectively classified into one of five categories: whistles (twenty-seven call types; Table 2), pulsed calls (thirteen call types; Table 3), noisy calls (one call type; Table 3), combined calls (five call types; Table 4) or clicks.

The overall trend in the discovery curve indicates that a complete vocal repertoire of the ECS belugas was not captured in this study. Depending on the randomized iteration and the order in which the calls were plotted, the steepness and asymptotic shape of the discovery curve varied. However, the average line suggests that the curve is still increasing and has not yet reached a complete asymptotic level (Figure 2).

Discovery Curve of the ECS Beluga Vocal Repertoire

Figure 2. Discovery curve illustrating the richness of the eastern Chukchi Sea (ECS) beluga vocal repertoire found in this study. The curve shows the number of unique call types versus the number of calls analyzed over 200 randomized iterations, with the discovery curve represented by a black line.

1. Whistles

The predominant call category in the ECS beluga vocal repertoire was whistles ($n = 682$), comprising 91.21% of the classified calls. Whistles were categorized by the shape of their fundamental frequency into eight whistle contours: ascending, r-shaped, descending, flat, modulated, n-shaped, trill, and u-shaped. Within each contour type, whistles were further subdivided by their structure (e.g., segmented), resulting in a total of twenty-seven call types.

Flat whistles ($n = 96$; 12.78% of total calls) and mostly flat whistles ($n = 93$; 12.38% of total calls) were the most frequent call types, establishing flat as the most prevalent contour category. The third most common call type was the descending whistle ($n = 68$; 9.05% of total calls), followed by the u-shaped whistle ($n = 63$; 8.39% of total calls). The n-shaped whistles ($n = 38$) comprised 5.06% of total calls, while all other call types not mentioned were each less than 5% of the captured vocal repertoire (Table 2). The newly added call type of a distinct segmented modulated whistle (i.e., modws.seg.b; $n = 21$) represented 2.79% of total calls. Another new call type documented was the pulsed n-shaped whistle (nws.pul; $n = 2$), which accounted for 0.27% of total calls (Table 2). In terms of whistle contour shape, those listed from most to least common were identified as flat (31.55% of total calls), descending (15.04% of total calls), modulated (13.98% of total calls),

u-shaped (10.39% of total calls), n-shaped (8.52% of total calls), ascending (8.26% of total calls), r-shaped (2.8% of total calls), and trill (0.67% of total calls) (Table 2). 10.70% of whistles were noted as having a terminal tail.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of whistles (mean \pm standard deviation) for the eastern Chukchi Sea beluga whale population, arranged according to contour shape. See Appendix 1, Table A for full name descriptions of the call types. Bandwidth is noted by ‘BW’ and pulse-repetition rate is abbreviated as ‘PRR’.

Call Type	N	% total calls	Duration (s)	Frequency (Hz)								
				Minimum	Maximum	BW	Peak	Start	End	Inflection	Break	Step
ahq	7	0.93	0.09 \pm 0.01	3710 \pm 1199	3846 \pm 1207	136 \pm 42	3765 \pm 1202	3719 \pm 1179	3775 \pm 1209	0.00	0.00	0.00
aws	40	5.33	0.64 \pm 0.34	2087 \pm 889	2562 \pm 924	475 \pm 436	2301 \pm 856	2090 \pm 892	2462 \pm 916	0.00	0.00	0.00
aws.seg	12	2.00	0.68 \pm 0.23	1515 \pm 643	2170 \pm 654	655 \pm 458	1825 \pm 735	1529 \pm 642	2068 \pm 646	0.00	0.58 \pm 0.67	1.33 \pm 1.30
rws	16	2.13	1.01 \pm 0.42	1787 \pm 701	2097 \pm 740	310 \pm 180	2045 \pm 733	1788 \pm 698	1988 \pm 737	0.00	0.00	0.00
rws.seg	5	0.67	0.99 \pm 0.43	3581 \pm 1655	3890 \pm 1694	319 \pm 66	3818 \pm 1706	3581 \pm 1656	3743 \pm 1691	0.00	1.60 \pm 1.67	0.80 \pm 0.45
dhq	6	0.80	0.09 \pm 0.01	2379 \pm 1486	2520 \pm 1468	141 \pm 31	2440 \pm 1471	2449 \pm 1457	2379 \pm 1485	0.00	0.00	0.00
dws	68	9.05	0.59 \pm 0.36	2629 \pm 1508	2958 \pm 1503	329 \pm 224	2774 \pm 1499	2873 \pm 1497	2635 \pm 1504	0.00	0.00	0.00
dws.seg	39	5.19	0.73 \pm 0.22	2289 \pm 1245	2885 \pm 1196	596 \pm 341	2501 \pm 1288	2784 \pm 1201	2305 \pm 1242	0.00	0.56 \pm 0.60	0.90 \pm 0.38
flatws	96	12.78	0.40 \pm 0.30	2418 \pm 1296	2495 \pm 1297	77 \pm 10	2456 \pm 1296	2420 \pm 1295	2420 \pm 1296	0.00	0.00	0.00
flatws.m	93	12.38	0.51 \pm 0.34	2380 \pm 1395	2493 \pm 1393	113 \pm 11	2437 \pm 1392	2397 \pm 1398	2396 \pm 1393	0.00	0.00	0.00
flatws.seg	16	2.13	0.71 \pm 0.26	2441 \pm 838	2549 \pm 833	108 \pm 19	2495 \pm 835	2457 \pm 845	2448 \pm 834	0.00	1.25 \pm 0.45	0.06 \pm 0.26
hq	32	4.26	0.07 \pm 0.01	3649 \pm 1823	3750 \pm 1814	101 \pm 28	3698 \pm 1818	3698 \pm 1818	3698 \pm 1818	0.00	0.00	0.00
modws	27	3.60	0.95 \pm 0.35	2291 \pm 779	2862 \pm 868	571 \pm 215	2460 \pm 738	2390 \pm 750	2391 \pm 770	4.04 \pm 1.19	0.00	0.00
modws.m	3	0.40	0.97 \pm 0.38	815 \pm 222	1856 \pm 93	1042 \pm 289	1445 \pm 384	1633 \pm 148	813 \pm 221	4.33 \pm 0.58	0.00	0.00
modws.S	26	3.46	0.64 \pm 0.26	2368 \pm 1562	2806 \pm 1501	438 \pm 269	2652 \pm 1522	2557 \pm 1552	2471 \pm 1534	2.00	0.00	0.00
modws.seg	28	3.73	0.78 \pm 0.26	1983 \pm 1770	2775 \pm 1634	792 \pm 399	2302 \pm 1710	2336 \pm 1742	2111 \pm 1818	3.75 \pm 1.51	0.50 \pm 0.69	1.29 \pm 1.05
modws.seg.b	21	2.79	0.93 \pm 0.13	1343 \pm 69	2309 \pm 115	965 \pm 107	1565 \pm 305	2022 \pm 221	1958 \pm 56	1.05 \pm 0.86	0.10 \pm 0.30	1.00
nws	38	5.06	0.53 \pm 0.39	2482 \pm 1650	2775 \pm 1608	293 \pm 168	2654 \pm 1624	2516 \pm 1637	2522 \pm 1636	1.00	0.00	0.00
nws.pul	2	0.27	0.67 \pm 0.05	539 \pm 180	2461 \pm 33	1922 \pm 213	2072 \pm 396	1969 \pm 52	539 \pm 180	1.00	0.00	0.00
nws.seg.b	6	0.80	0.84 \pm 0.19	1855 \pm 941	2277 \pm 713	422 \pm 261	2179 \pm 743	1953 \pm 850	1894 \pm 945	1.00	1.50 \pm 0.84	1.50 \pm 0.55
nws.seg.c	11	1.46	0.71 \pm 0.25	2235 \pm 1266	2617 \pm 1263	382 \pm 168	2396 \pm 1196	2350 \pm 1292	2271 \pm 1262	1.00	0.64 \pm 0.50	0.55 \pm 0.52
nws.seg.d	7	0.93	1.00 \pm 0.35	1888 \pm 873	2418 \pm 520	530 \pm 365	2077 \pm 742	1944 \pm 841	1907 \pm 888	1.00	1.57 \pm 1.40	2.29 \pm 0.49
trill	5	0.67	0.72 \pm 0.23	3958 \pm 1949	4269 \pm 2083	310 \pm 200	4058 \pm 1929	4113 \pm 2092	4107 \pm 2095	1.20 \pm 2.68	4.60 \pm 3.58	1.20 \pm 1.30
uws	63	8.39	0.63 \pm 0.39	2479 \pm 1109	2796 \pm 1060	317 \pm 188	2602 \pm 1109	2648 \pm 1052	2673 \pm 1085	1.00	0.00	0.00
uws.seg.b	3	0.40	0.63 \pm 0.34	2474 \pm 315	3139 \pm 237	665 \pm 178	2789 \pm 107	3027 \pm 281	2982 \pm 319	1.00	0.67 \pm 1.15	2.00 \pm 0.00
uws.seg.c	10	1.33	0.54 \pm 0.31	3584 \pm 2068	3921 \pm 2033	338 \pm 169	3695 \pm 2012	3793 \pm 2023	3751 \pm 2067	1.00	0.70 \pm 0.48	1.00 \pm 0.82
uws.seg.d	2	0.27	1.16 \pm 0.13	2623 \pm 1401	4429 \pm 3372	1806 \pm 1971	2936 \pm 1346	4247 \pm 3470	2969 \pm 1389	1.00	1.50 \pm 2.12	2.50 \pm 2.12

2. Pulsed calls, noisy calls, and clicks

The second most predominant call category in the ECS beluga vocal repertoire is pulsed calls ($n = 47$), accounting for 6.25% of the total calls. Pulsed calls were differentiated by their pulse-repetition rate and their contour shape. Pulse type A calls (pulse.A; $n = 6$; 0.80% of total calls) had a scream-like aural impression with the highest pulse-repetition rate. In addition to descending pulse type A calls (pulse.A.d; $n = 6$; 0.80% of total calls), two new call types were documented based on contour shape: the n-shaped pulse type A call (pulse.A.n; $n = 1$; 0.13% of total calls), and the u-shaped pulse type A call (pulse.A.u; $n = 1$; 0.13% of total calls) (Table 3; Appendix 1, Figure B). The pulse type I calls (pulse.I; $n = 19$; 2.53% of total calls) were the most prevalent pulsed call type. N-shaped (pulse.I.n) and u-shaped (pulse.I.u) pulse type I calls were also added as new call types. Pulse type I calls were subdivided by contour shape into ascending (pulse.I.a; $n = 2$; 0.27% of total calls), descending (pulse.I.d; $n = 5$; 0.67% of total calls), n-shaped (pulse.I.n; $n = 1$; 0.13% of total calls), and u-shaped (pulse.I.u; $n = 1$; 0.13% of total calls) (Table 3; Appendix 1, Figure C). A new pulse type R call (pulse.R) was also documented with a distinct r-shaped contour, accounting for 0.27% of the total calls ($n = 2$). Segmented pulsed calls were identified in both pulse type I calls (i.e., pulse.I.a.seg and pulse.I.seg) and pulse type R calls (i.e., pulse.R.seg; $n=2$). Each of these was assigned as a new call type and, collectively, the segmented pulsed calls represented 0.39% of total calls (Table 3).

Additionally, the call category of noisy calls represented 1.86% of the total calls ($n = 14$). Restricted frequency click series ($n = 0$) were observed in the recordings; however, none were annotated because they did not meet the requirements to be included in this study (e.g., could not confidently determine the top or bottom of the entire sound).

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of pulsed and noisy calls (mean \pm standard deviation) from the eastern Chukchi Sea beluga whale population. Bandwidth is noted by ‘BW’ and pulse repetition rate is abbreviated as ‘PRR’.

Call Type	N	% total calls	Duration (s)	Frequency (Hz)									PRR
				Minimum	Maximum	BW	Peak	Start	End	Inflection	Break	Step	
noisy	14	1.86	0.80 \pm 0.23	2526 \pm 1299	3990 \pm 1632	1464 \pm 849	3213 \pm 1508	3160 \pm 1585	3272 \pm 1526	0.07 \pm 0.25	0.00	0.00	N/A
pulse.A	6	0.80	0.70 \pm 0.12	2064 \pm 1364	3257 \pm 1376	1193 \pm 680	2771 \pm 1197	2653 \pm 1340	2425 \pm 1576	0.00	0.00	0.00	222 \pm 57
pulse.A.d	6	0.80	0.87 \pm 0.19	1707 \pm 199	4346 \pm 130	2639 \pm 216	3005 \pm 89	3235 \pm 104	2687 \pm 138	0.00	0.00	0.00	354 \pm 59
pulse.A.n	1	0.13	0.84	2621	3832	1211	3296	3056	2938	1.00	0.00	0.00	293
pulse.A.u	1	0.13	0.86	2150	3930	1780	2368	3772	3550	1.00	0.00	0.00	198
pulse.I	19	2.53	0.95 \pm 0.31	2129 \pm 1413	4032 \pm 1640	1903 \pm 1640	2700 \pm 1473	2762 \pm 1501	2725 \pm 1479	0.00	0.00	0.00	82 \pm 15
pulse.I.a	2	0.27	1.07 \pm 0.21	1057 \pm 235	3428 \pm 64.01	2371 \pm 299	2368 \pm 520	1103 \pm 171	1891 \pm 1035	0.00	0.00	0.00	157 \pm 42
pulse.I.a.seg	1	0.13	0.89	3537	5416	1880	4896	3537	4631	0.00	1.00	0.00	105
pulse.I.d	5	0.67	0.85 \pm 0.24	3780 \pm 1529	5332 \pm 1295	1552 \pm 412	4662 \pm 1318	4981 \pm 1308	4189 \pm 1761	0.00	0.0	0.0	138 \pm 41
pulse.I.n	1	0.13	1.35	1046	2220	1174	1760	1451	1046	1.00	0.00	2.00	154
pulse.I.seg	1	0.13	1.02	1532	2250	718	1744	1744	1744	0.00	1.00	0.00	75
pulse.I.u	1	0.13	1.11	4235	6894	2660	5728	6349	5450	1.00	0.00	1.00	133
pulse.R	2	0.27	0.94 \pm 0.11	1369 \pm 67	1783 \pm 39	414 \pm 28	1600	1369 \pm 67	1560 \pm 11	0.00	0.00	0.00	99 \pm 2
pulse.R.seg	1	0.13	1.21	1045	1745	700	1648	1045	1545	1.00	0.00	1.00	87

3. Combined calls

The least predominant call category in the ECS beluga vocal repertoire was combined calls ($n = 8$), contributing to only 1.05% of the total calls. Five new combined call types were documented. Among these, ECS.c.4 ($n = 4$; 0.53% of total calls) was the only combined call type observed more than three times, meeting the repetition requirements for a new call type implemented in the whistle, pulsed call, or noisy call category (following Brewer et al., 2023 and Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b). In contrast, ECS.c.1, ECS.c.2, ECS.c.3, and ECS.c.5 were all annotated once and each accounted for 0.13% of the total calls (Table 4). Although these combined call types were documented less than three times, they were still reported and treated as distinct, in line with the methodology of Brewer et al. (2023). However, since these calls did not meet the same repetition standards as other call categories (e.g., whistles), it cannot be certain whether these combined calls originate from one individual versus two animals simultaneously vocalizing. ECS.c.2 and ECS.c.3 were documented approximately 2.5 seconds apart but were placed as separate call types due to the contours of their whistle components. ECS.c.2 had a modulated whistle component, whereas ECS.c.3 had a flat whistle component (Appendix 1, Figure D). For ECS.c.4 ($n = 4$),

this call type was observed in a sequence, increasing confidence that this is a combined call emitted by an individual. ECS.c.5 was the only combined call type to have a pulsed component first and then a whistle component. The other combined call types began with a whistle component and then a pulsed component (Appendix 1, Figure D). No combined call types with two whistle components were found.

Table 4. Descriptive statistics of the combined call types (mean \pm standard deviation) from the eastern Chukchi Sea beluga whale population. The asterisk denotes the combined call types that were not observed more than three times (i.e., did not meet the repetition protocol requirement). Following Brewer et al. (2023), the combined calls are still noted here for future studies. Bandwidth is noted by ‘BW’ and pulse repetition rate is abbreviated as ‘PRR’.

Call Type	N	Whole call		Whistle component									Pulsed component								
		% total calls	Dur. (s)	Frequency (Hz)									Frequency (Hz)								
				Min.	Max.	BW	Peak	Start	End	Inflect.	Break	Step	Dur. (s)	Min.	Max.	BW	Peak	Start	End	PRR	Dur. (s)
ECS.c.1*	1	0.13	1.22	1010	1943	934	1456	1234	1033	3.00	0.00	0.00	0.71	1006	2160	1155	2048	1986	1742	58	0.55
ECS.c.2*	1	0.13	1.11	4239	4759	521	4288	4258	4451	2.00	0.00	0.00	0.35	3407	4966	1559	4416	4355	4248	142	0.76
ECS.c.3*	1	0.13	1.04	4233	4374	141	4336	4297	4233	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.18	2434	4779	2345	3552	3552	3552	123	0.87
ECS.c.4	4	0.53	1.05 ± 0.04	1413 ± 171	3028 ± 163	1615 ± 290	1472 ± 217	1413 ± 171	2460 ± 477	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.27 ± 0.04	1549 ± 102	2291 ± 17	742 ± 89	1908 ± 200	1859 ± 190	1822 ± 195	87 ± 10	0.77 ± 0.04
ECS.c.5*	1	0.13	0.80	1405	1530	126	1456	1404	1454	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.56	1219	1427	208	1280	1280	1280	68	0.24

B. Quantitative classification of call types

RF Model agreed with the manual classification of call types for the ECS beluga vocal repertoire 78.8% of the time (Table 5). For the growth of the RF Model’s decision trees, the four most important variables ranked in order were: the number of inflections (average mean decrease in Gini Index = 21.70), bandwidth (average mean decrease in Gini Index = 20.67), frequency trend (average mean decrease in Gini Index = 16.68) and duration (average mean decrease in Gini Index = 15.91) (Appendix 1, Table C). Most of the RF Model’s misclassifications compared to the manual classification of call types emerged for whistles with single inflection points (i.e., u-shaped versus n-shaped) and similar frequency trends (i.e., ascending versus r-shaped) (Table 5). U-shaped and segmented u-shaped whistles had the highest misclassification error rate of 50% and were mostly mistaken for n-shaped and segmented n-shaped whistles. This highlights the model’s difficulty in discriminating between whistles with the same number of inflection points (i.e., one). Of the seventeen call types, the model predicted thirteen call types with an accuracy of 70% or higher.

Table 5. Confusion matrix and call type error rate for the Random Forest (RF) Model’s performance on predicting the test data sets, combined from each iteration of the three-fold cross-validation. The Random Forest Model correctly classified 78.8% of calls. The first column shows the call types from the manual classification (see Appendix 1, Table A for full name descriptions). Each following columns shows the predicted call type (15 calls per call type) with the rows depicting the true call type. The final column lists the call type error rate.

Confusion matrix:

Test Predictions	aws	dws	dws.seg	flatws	flatws.m	flatws.seg	hq	modws	modws.S	modws.seg	modws.seg.b	nws	nws.seg	pulse.I	rws	uws	uws.seg	Call type error
aws	9	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	5	1	0	0.4
dws	0	15	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0
dws.seg	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2
flatws	0	0	0	12	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2
flatws.m	2	0	0	1	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0.2
flatws.seg	0	0	1	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0
hq	0	0	0	2	0	0	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.1
modws	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.1
modws.S	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.3
modws.seg	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.1
modws.seg.b	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0
nws	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	11	1	0	0	6	0	0.3
nws.seg	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	10	0	0	0	8	0.3
pulse.I	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0.0
rws	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0.4
uws	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	8	0	0.5
uws.seg	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	4	0	0	0	7	0.5

C. Repertoire comparison

From the original ECS dataset of 751 calls, which was randomized and consisted of up to the first 100 calls in each day, 750 calls were randomly selected to evenly split the data into three groups of 250 calls each. To prepare the BS beluga dataset, 1,019 calls were randomized and 750 calls were selected to complement the ECS data. Once the dataset was combined for the Population RF Model, fifty-two call types were identified.

The Population RF Model correctly classified 78.0% of beluga calls to population. In other words, the model was able to predict the call’s population 28.0% better than random chance (i.e., 50%) (Table 6). The Population RF Model was slightly more accurate at predicting the true population for ECS beluga calls (21% error rate) than for BS beluga calls (23% error rate). The three most important variables contributing to the Population RF Model’s development were frequency trend (average mean decrease in Gini Index = 72.37), duration (average mean decrease in Gini Index = 62.81), and then bandwidth (average mean decrease in Gini Index = 56.23) (Appendix 1, Table D). These findings were significantly greater than chance, $\chi^2(1, N = 1500) = 462.04, p < .001$.

Table 6. Confusion matrix for the Population Random Forest (RF) Model’s performance on predicting the test data sets, combined from each iteration of the three-fold cross-validation. The overall error rate in classification is 22.0%. The columns indicate the classifier’s predicted population and the rows show the true population of the call. The final column lists the classification error rate for each population.

Confusion matrix:			
Population	BS	ECS	Error rate
BS	596	180	0.23
ECS	154	570	0.21

For both the ECS and BS beluga vocal repertoires, the most prevalent call type was a whistle. Flat whistles (flatws; 12.78% of the total calls), followed by mostly flat whistles (flatws.m; 12.38% of total calls), were the most frequently used call types for the ECS belugas (Table 2). In contrast, the flat whistle was the seventh most used call type for the BS belugas (4.61% of the total calls). In the BS beluga vocal repertoire, the most common call type was the descending whistle (11.87% of total calls) with the mostly flat whistle (8.93% of total calls) being second (Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b, p. 3059, Figure 2). The descending contour overall was also frequently used by the ECS belugas, with descending whistles (dws; 9.05% of total calls) and segmented descending whistles (dws.seg; 5.19% of total calls) comprising 14.24% of their total calls (Table 2). The BS beluga vocal repertoire consisted of more high squeaks (hq; 7.16% of total calls) and messy modulated whistles (modws.m; 3.43% of total calls) compared to the ECS belugas (4.26% and 0.40% of total calls respectively) (Table 2; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b, p. 3059, Figure 2). U-shaped whistles slightly were more prevalent in the ECS belugas’ vocal repertoire (uws; 8.39% for ECS; 6.67% for BS) (Table 2). Both populations similarly used ascending whistles (aws, 6.87% for BS, 5.33% for ECS), n-shaped whistles (nws, 4.42% for BS, 5.06% for ECS), and modulated segmented whistles (modws.seg, 3.83% for BS, 3.73% for ECS) (Table 2; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b, p. 3059, Figure 2). Call types identified for the ECS belugas but not in the BS belugas vocal repertoire included: a specific segmented n-shaped whistle (nws.seg.d, 0.93% of total calls), the newly added pulsed n-shaped whistle (nws.pul, 0.27% of total calls), and a new segmented modulated whistle (modws.seg.b, 2.79% of total calls) (Table 2). Call types with a segmented structure (e.g., flatws.seg; dws.seg; nws.seg.c) were overall used less frequently for both populations than non-

segmented call types within the same contour (Table 2; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b, p. 3059, Figure 2). However, for the ECS belugas, the modulated segmented whistles (modws.seg and modws.seg.b) comprised more of their total calls (6.52% combined) than the modulated whistle (3.60% of total calls) (Table 2).

After whistles, pulsed calls were the next most prevalent vocalization family in both the ECS and BS beluga vocal repertoires, followed by noisy calls, and finally combined calls. Pulsed and noisy calls represented 11.48% of the total calls in the BS beluga vocal repertoire (Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b, p. 3061, Table III), whereas for the ECS belugas, they comprised 6.25% of the total calls (Table 3). For both populations, pulse type I calls were more prevalent than pulse type A calls (Table 3; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b, p. 3061). N-shaped, u-shaped, and r-shaped pulsed calls were not described or in the naming scheme for the BS beluga vocal repertoire, making comparison difficult since these were all newly added pulsed call types for the ECS beluga vocal repertoire. Noisy calls were not used often; however, they were more commonly found in the ECS beluga vocal repertoire (1.86% of total calls; Table 3) than the BS beluga vocal repertoire (0.20% of total calls; Garland Castellote and Berchok, 2015b, p. 3061). For combined calls, there were six combined calls attributed to the BS belugas (2.54% combined total; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b, p. 3062, Table IV) and for the ECS belugas, five combined calls were identified (1.05% combined total; Table 4). Only one of the combined calls was observed more than three times (ECS.c.4) in the ECS belugas' calls and for the BS belugas, four out of six combined calls were present in the dataset three or more times ($n \geq 3$). None of the combined calls identified for the BS belugas were present in the ECS beluga vocal repertoire.

To create the Whistle-based Population RF Model, 682 whistles were identified out of 751 calls in the ECS dataset, and for the BS dataset, there 874 whistles out of 1,019 calls. Both datasets were then randomly subsampled for 678 whistles each, in order to create the three even groups (i.e., 226 in each group). In total, twenty-six call types were identified.

The Whistle-based Population RF Model correctly classified each whistle's true population 79.5% of the time (Table 7). The classification accuracy rates for both populations were similar, with 80.0% for ECS belugas and 79.0% for BS belugas' whistles. Frequency trend (average mean decrease in Gini Index = 68.76) ranked as the most important variable for construction the Whistle-based Population RF Model's decision trees. The second and third most influential variables were duration (average mean decrease in Gini Index = 58.89) and bandwidth (average mean decrease in Gini Index = 55.50) (Appendix 1, Table E). These findings were significantly greater than chance, $\chi^2(1, N = 1356) = 467.37, p < .001$.

Table 7. Confusion matrix for the Whistle-based Population Random Forest (RF) Model’s performance on predicting the test data set, combined from each iteration of the three-fold cross-validation. The overall error rate in classification is 20.5%. The columns indicate the classifier’s predicted population and the rows show the true population of the call. The final column lists the classification error rate for each population.

Confusion matrix:			
Population	BS	ECS	Error rate
BS	543	145	0.21
ECS	135	533	0.20

IV. Discussion

The present study’s results show the ECS and BS belugas can be acoustically recognized at the population level. To begin with, this research provides the first description of the vocal repertoire of the eastern Chukchi Sea beluga whales during their autumn migration. Additionally, the present work is the first to quantitatively compare the vocal repertoires of two sympatric, genetically-distinct beluga whale populations in Alaska. The Random Forest analysis correctly classified 78.0% of calls to population, and more specifically, also accurately assigned 79.5% of whistles to population. These results show there are call characteristics and patterns in call type usage in the ECS and BS beluga vocal repertoires that are population-specific.

For the ECS belugas, the first description of their vocal repertoire was incomplete, as the discovery curve illustrated with a slope that had not yet reached its asymptotic level (Figure 2). Specifically, the vocalizations captured for this study reflect the ECS beluga calls during migration. The frequency of using call types may vary based on behavioral states (Sjare and Smith, 1986a; Weilgart and Whitehead, 1990), therefore, the trend in the ECS belugas’ discovery curve highlights that other call types, not used in migration, are likely a part of their vocal repertoire. Both the ECS and Cook Inlet belugas’ discovery curves share a similar slope until 751 calls (i.e., the sample size for this study) (Figure 2; Brewer, et al., 2023, p. 3492), with the Cook Inlet belugas’ trend illustrating an almost complete repertoire at 1,626 calls. The ECS beluga calls were divided into forty-six subjective call types (Appendix 1, Table A), similar to the forty-one documented in the Cook Inlet beluga vocal repertoire and more than the thirty-six identified for the BS belugas (Brewer et al., 2023;

Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b). The differences in the number of call types between the most recently described beluga vocal repertoires reflect the inherent subjectivity in the nomenclature for a graded call system. The beluga whale naming scheme is derived from that used for the North Atlantic pilot whale (*Globicephala melaena*), another odontocete with a graded call structure, following a grouping approach based on frequency contour and different aspects of call structure (Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b; Sjare and Smith, 1986b). Modifications of this naming scheme are subjective assessments of how broadly the observer defines and categorizes the call types (Au and Hastings, 2008). While this approach establishes a useful baseline for comparison, it may not reflect the call characteristics significant to the beluga whales themselves (Chmelnitsky and Ferguson, 2012).

Across the described beluga vocal repertoires worldwide, the flat contoured whistles are the most prevalent either as the first or second predominant call type (Brewer, et al., 2023; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b). Flat whistles were also the most frequently used call type in the ECS beluga vocal repertoire (12.78% of total calls) (Table 2). Mostly flat whistles were the second most common call type for the ECS belugas (Table 2) and also for the BS and Churchill River (Canada) beluga populations (Chmelnitsky and Ferguson, 2012, p. 4825; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b, p. 3059). Cook Inlet belugas' second most common call type was the flat whistle, although their naming scheme did not also subdivide into messy flat whistles (Brewer, et al., 2023). Descending whistles ranked third as the most prevalent call type for ECS belugas (Table 2) and first for both the Cook Inlet (Brewer, et al., 2023, p. 3495) and BS belugas (Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b, p. 3059). For the Churchill River belugas, their most common call type was an r-shaped whistle, noted as an “ascending then flat” whistle (10.3% of total calls; Chmelnitsky and Ferguson, 2012, p. 4825), while r-shaped whistles were only 2.13% of total calls for the ECS belugas (Table 2).

In terms of repertoire composition, pulsed and noisy calls comprised a small proportion of the ECS beluga vocal repertoire (8.11% of total calls; Table 3) compared to other populations, such as Svalbard (31.3% of total calls; Karlsen, et al., 2002, p. 813, Table 2), Churchill River (25.9% of total calls; Chmelnitsky and Ferguson, 2012, p. 4825), Cook Inlet (22.1% of total calls; pulsed calls only; Brewer, et al., 2023, p. 3497), and Cunningham Inlet (21.5% of total calls; Sjare and Smith, 1986b, p. 408, 412). Additionally, six to seven combined calls were noted for the BS (Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b, p. 3062), Churchill River (Chmelnitsky and Ferguson, 2012, p. 4827), and Svalbard (Karlsen, et al.,

2002, p. 813, Table 3) belugas, which is a similar amount to the five combined call types noted in the ECS beluga vocal repertoire, with the caveat that only one out of the five was annotated more than three times (Table 4). None of the ECS combined call types were observed in other populations.

Thus far, comparisons between beluga vocal repertoires have focused on similarities and differences in call types and their patterns of frequency use. The conclusions drawn from these comparisons are restricted by inconsistent methodological approaches throughout the years (Chmelnitsky and Ferguson, 2012; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b). To ensure a compatible comparison, the present study described the ECS beluga vocal repertoire following the same classification scheme and analytical method as used for the BS beluga vocal repertoire (Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b). Furthermore, the acoustic recordings collected for this study were also used in two prior publications regarding beluga whales in Alaska, including the analysis of the BS beluga vocal repertoire (Garland, Berchok and Castellote, 2015a; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b).

Although there was no visual confirmation of the belugas' behavior, both populations were presumed to be migrating given the time of year and recorder location. The compositions of the ECS and BS beluga vocal repertoires were similar in terms of vocalization family, with whistles comprising the majority for both repertoires (i.e., 91.3% of ECS total calls and 85.7% of BS total calls). To date, there is no clear correlation between certain beluga whistle call types compared to a specific behavioral state (Panova, et al., 2019; Sjare and Smith, 1986a; Faucher, 1988). However, flat stereotyped tonal signals are hypothesized to be used in situations of long-range communication (Panova, et al., 2012). The lower frequency of the flat contoured whistles identified in both vocal repertoires (i.e., mean frequency ≤ 3 kHz) as a primary or second most common call type (Table 2; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b, p. 3059) may allow the migrating pods to maintain contact or facilitate group cohesion over larger distances because lower frequencies propagate farther in water (Tyack and Janik, 2013). In terms of more complex signaling, the two newly described whistles for the ECS belugas, a pulsed n-shaped whistle (nws.pul) and a unique segmented modulated whistle (modws.seg.b) (Appendix 1, Figure A), were observed in sequences and not described for the BS belugas. These could be population-specific ECS beluga calls or possibly the BS belugas also use these call types, but it was not observed in the same manner to be noted as a unique call type category. More data is needed to confirm this and the specific meaning behind these whistles for the ECS belugas is unknown. Vocalizations emitted in sequences likely carry more information than the same call vocalized once

(Walmsley, et al., 2020). Although sequences were not explicitly investigated during this study or for the BS belugas, the rhythmic repetition of these two newly described whistles could possibly play a role in group cohesion, recognition, or coordination among the ECS belugas (Walmsley, et al., 2020).

Compared to other populations previously mentioned (e.g., Svalbard, 31.3% of total calls, Karlsen, et al., 2002), both the ECS and BS beluga vocal repertoires consisted of a smaller percentage of pulsed and noisy calls (i.e., 8.11% and 11.48% of total calls, respectively) (Table 3; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b, p. 3061). Pulsed calls have been noted as frequently used during close social interactions for the Cunningham Inlet (Sjare and Smith, 1986a), White Sea (Russia) (Panova, et al., 2012), and the St. Lawrence Estuary (Faucher, 1988) beluga populations. The similarly limited proportion of pulsed and noisy calls for the ECS and BS belugas may be a function of their migratory behavior compared to the higher proportions found in the compositions of beluga vocal repertoires described from social aggregations (e.g., Chmelnitsky and Ferguson, 2012).

While the ECS and BS beluga vocal repertoires shared similarities in their overall composition, the results presented in this study show their population identities can be determined based on their call characteristics. Whistles were explored further, in particular, because they comprised the majority vocalization family of both vocal repertoires. Both the Population RF Model and Whistle-based Population RF Model were able to predict to a population level with similar accuracy (i.e., 78.0% and 79.5%), indicating the pulsed, noisy, and combined calls were not the driving force in differentiating between the two populations. The models' classification accuracy improved slightly when focused on the whistles. The Whistle-based Population RF Model was most likely to identify the whistle to its true population by examining frequency trend, duration, and bandwidth. Patterns in each variable depended on call type with some overlap.

For the BS belugas, descending contoured whistles had a higher mean frequency trend (ratio) (dhq, ECS = 1.05, BS = 1.13; dws, ECS = 1.13, BS = 1.40; dws.seg, ECS = 1.26, BS = 1.53) because of their higher start frequencies (Appendix 1, Tables A and F). For example, descending whistles (dws) for BS belugas had a mean start frequency of 3169 Hz and it was 2873 Hz for the ECS belugas. Both populations shared similar mean end frequencies of 2365 Hz (ECS) and 2363 Hz (BS). For most ascending contoured whistles, BS belugas had a lower mean frequency trend, indicating a higher mean end frequency relative to the call's mean start frequency (ahq = ECS = 0.99, BS = 0.76; aws, ECS = 0.84, BS = 0.72; rws, ECS = 0.90, BS = 0.81; rws.seg, ECS = 0.95, BS = 0.77) (Appendix 1, Table F).

For ECS belugas, their messy modulated whistle had a mean frequency trend of more than double that of the BS belugas (modws.m, ECS = 2.12, BS = 1.02), showing a more pronounced descending trend. Whistles with flat (e.g., flatws.m), n-shaped (e.g., nws.seg.b), and most u-shaped (uws, uws.seg.c) contours had a similar mean frequency trend between the populations (Appendix 1, Table F).

Whistles with an ascending contour had a longer mean duration in the ECS beluga vocal repertoire. Mean duration in seconds (sec.) for each population's ascending contoured whistles were as follows: aws (ECS = 0.64; BS = 0.46), aws.seg (ECS = 0.68; BS = 0.42), rws (ECS = 1.01, BS = 0.64), rws.seg (ECS = 0.99; BS = 0.74). The n-shaped whistle for both populations had the same mean duration of 0.53 seconds (Table 2; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b, p. 3059). While the two segmented n-shaped whistles (nws.seg.b, nws.seg.c) both had longer mean durations (sec.) for the ECS belugas (nws.seg.b, ECS = 0.84, BS = 0.62; nws.seg.c, ECS = 0.71, BS = 0.34). Segmented flat whistles also had a longer mean duration for ECS belugas (0.71 sec.) than that of the BS belugas (0.55 sec.). Finally, descending whistles, the BS belugas predominant call type, had a longer mean duration in the ECS belugas of 0.59 seconds (BS = 0.47 sec.) (Table 2; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b, p. 3059). Both populations had similar mean durations for modulated whistles (modws, modws.S, modws.seg), certain flat contoured whistles (flatws, flatws.m), the u-shaped whistle (uws), the segmented descending whistle (dws.seg), and different high squeaks (ahq, dhq, hq). Notably, the trill was the only call type in the BS beluga vocal repertoire with a mean duration exceeding that of the ECS belugas by more than 0.10 seconds (ECS = 0.72; BS = 0.86) (Table 2; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b, p. 3059).

On average, the majority of call types with a wider frequency bandwidth can be attributed to the BS belugas. Both populations had similar mean frequency bandwidths for some whistles within the ascending (aws, aws.seg, rws), flat (flatws, flatws.m, flatws.seg), and modulated (modws) contours (Table 2; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b, p. 3059). The mean bandwidth of the segmented descending whistles (dws.seg) from the BS beluga vocal repertoire (909 Hz, n = 27) was over 300 Hz greater than that of the ECS belugas (596 Hz, n = 39). For the segmented n-shaped whistles (nws.seg.c), defined by one break in the call's structure, the mean bandwidth was over 600 Hz higher in the BS beluga calls (1057 Hz, n = 12) than that of ECS beluga calls (382 Hz, n = 11). The only call type from the ECS belugas with an average bandwidth greater than that of the BS beluga calls (i.e., a difference of more than 100 Hz) was the messy modulated whistle (modws.m, ECS = 1042 Hz, BS = 609 Hz) (Table 2; Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b, p. 3059). Taken

together, these noted differences between populations varied by call type within their whistles' frequency trend, duration, and bandwidth, supporting the models' findings. The differences were found to be significantly higher than chance, providing the first evidence of population-specific characteristics in the vocal repertoires of the ECS and BS belugas.

A complete acoustic divergence between these two populations was not found, as some overlap appeared between characteristics of certain call types. Given the ECS and BS belugas geographically overlap, they likely originate from a more recent common ancestor than the other three sub-Arctic populations in Alaska, which is theorized to contribute to a higher likelihood of call similarity (Filatova, et al., 2012). The observed differences might reflect cumulative changes in specific call types over time that are adopted by each population and passed down generationally (Ford, 1991). When populations are sympatric, these acoustic differences are considered group-specific dialects. Dialects have been shown in the vocal repertoires of killer whales (*Orcinus orca*) and sperm whales (*Physeter macrocephalus*) (Ford, 2018), but never before described in beluga whales. Both the ECS and BS belugas have a strong cultural migratory behavior, with high site fidelity to discrete wintering and summering grounds using routes that appear to be matrilineally learned (O'Corry-Crowe, et al., 2018). Combined with their gregarious nature, demonstrated ability as vocal learners (Ridgway, et al., 2012), and their proven genetic separation (O'Corry-Crowe, et al., 2018), these acoustic differences may provide initial evidence for the occurrence of vocal dialects between the ECS and BS belugas.

Along with these findings, the limitations of this study should be taken into consideration. In describing the ECS beluga vocal repertoire, the sample size of 751 calls is small compared to other described beluga vocal repertoires (e.g., Cook Inlet = 1,633 calls) (Brewer, et al., 2023). A higher number of calls were present during the recording period of eleven days, but the smaller sample size reflects adherence to the rule of only selecting non-overlapping calls for annotation. The sample size was further reduced to create a balanced dataset for training the RF Model classifier in a three-fold cross-validation. There was not enough time to explore additional options for reinforcing the manual classification of call types, such as conducting an inter-observer reliability test. However, when possible, an expert in the field was consulted to review various manual classifications of call types to assess perceptual agreement. Another acknowledged limitation is the described ECS beluga vocal repertoire represents only those belugas indicating their presence vocally while migrating, specifically during the 2010 autumn season. Additionally, without visual

verification, their behavior presumed throughout this sampling period is migration, given the specific time of year (Garland, Castellote and Berchok, 2015b).

Future work should investigate the ECS beluga vocal repertoire across multiple years, in different behavioral contexts, and their use of sequences to ensure a more complete understanding of their repertoire is captured. This study also revealed that the ECS and BS belugas can be acoustically differentiated to the population level, which may be reflective of dialectical differences; however, more research investigating this across several years in differing contexts needs to be completed before a definitive claim of dialects can be asserted. Furthermore, as the ECS belugas number close to one-third of the BS belugas (Young, et al., 2023), the population-specific characteristics in both vocal repertoires described here have wide implications for the management of each population. Federal agencies can now use this information along with passive acoustic monitoring to identify which specific population is present nearby. For example, when the populations temporarily overlap in September, in the Beaufort Sea, if there was a dataset of annotated calls from an unknown population, NOAA NFMS could examine the whistles using the Whistle-based Population RF Model to help determine whether the whistles were from the ECS or BS beluga population. This information could also be used by key stakeholders in the oil, gas, and commercial shipping industries to assess how each population is affected by the ramifications of their ever-increasing presence in the Arctic (e.g., oil spills, noise). Particularly in harsh environments, such as the Arctic Ocean, where conducting visual surveys is not always feasible, remotely monitoring cryptic populations in this manner is an effective, non-invasive method that is relatively cost-effective (Garland, Berchok and Castellote, 2015a; Sousa-Lima, et al., 2013).

In conclusion, this study provides the first evidence that population identity is encoded in the vocal repertoires of the ECS and BS belugas whales through differences in their call characteristics and patterns in call type usage. Also presented here is the first description of the ECS beluga vocal repertoire, contributing to a baseline for future studies investigating their calls in other behavioral contexts. Both findings helped establish a foundation for future work to expand upon exploring the geographic variability in the beluga vocal repertoires throughout Alaska. Furthermore, this study's comparative approach using Random Forest analysis also provides a framework for comparison of future beluga vocal repertoires worldwide. These findings contribute a small piece to the larger puzzle of understanding the intricacies of beluga whale communication and the variability within the vocal repertoires of social toothed whales, ultimately providing valuable insight for population structure, management, and conservation efforts.

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Appendix 1:

Table A. Descriptions of each call types' full name in the eastern Chukchi Sea beluga vocal repertoire, based on the naming scheme developed by Garland, Castellotte, and Berchok (2015b) and Sjare and Smith (1986b). For examples of Type A and Type I pulsed tones, see Sjare and Smith (1986b), p. 413.

Call Type	Full name description
ahq	Ascending high squeak
aws	Ascending whistle
aws.seg	Segmented (broken) ascending whistle
rws	R-shaped whistle
rws.seg	Segmented (broken) r-shaped whistle
dhq	Descending high squeak
dws	Descending whistle
dws.seg	Segmented (broken) descending whistle
flatws	Flat whistle
flatws.m	Mostly flat whistle
flatws.seg	Segmented (broken) flat whistle
hq	High squeak
modws	Modulated whistle
modws.m	Messy modulated whistle
modws.S	Short modulated whistle
modws.seg	Segmented (broken) modulated whistle
modws.seg.b	Segmented (broken) modulated whistle
nws	N-shaped whistle
nws.pul	Pulsed n-shaped whistle
nws.seg.b	Segmented (broken) n-shaped whistle
nws.seg.c	Segmented (broken) n-shaped whistle
nws.seg.d	Segmented (broken) n-shaped whistle
trill	Trill
uws	U-shaped whistle
uws.seg.b	Segmented (broken) u-shaped whistle

uws.seg.c	Segmented (broken) u-shaped whistle
uws.seg.d	Segmented (broken) u-shaped whistle
pulse.A	Type A - pulsed cries/screams
pulse.A.d	Type A - descending cries/screams
pulse.A.n	Type A - n-shaped cries/screams
pulse.A.u	Type A - u-shaped cries/screams
pulse.I	Type I - pulsed tones
pulse.I.a	Type I - ascending pulsed tones
pulse.I.d	Type I - descending pulsed tones
pulse.I.n	Type I - n-shaped pulsed tones
pulse.I.u	Type I - u-shaped pulsed tones
pulse.I.seg	Type I - segmented (broken) pulsed call
pulse.R	R-shaped pulsed call
pulse.R.seg	Segmented (broken) r-shaped pulsed call
noisy	Noisy
click	Frequency restricted click series
ECS.c.1	Eastern Chukchi Sea combined call type 1
ECS.c.2	Eastern Chukchi Sea combined call type 2
ECS.c.3	Eastern Chukchi Sea combined call type 3
ECS.c.4	Eastern Chukchi Sea combined call type 4
ECS.c.5	Eastern Chukchi Sea combined call type 5

Table B. A comprehensive list of measurements and rules used in manual and quantitative classification of call types for the eastern Chukchi Sea beluga whales.

Sound measurements	Rule						
Start Frequency (Hz)	Measured using Raven Pro’s cursor positioned at the fundamental’s bottom edge.						
End Frequency (Hz)	Measured using Raven Pro’s cursor positioned at the fundamental’s bottom edge.						
Inflection Points (#)	A change in modulation (from positive to negative slope or from negative to positive slope) greater than 100 Hz or 0.01 kHz.						
Breaks (#)	Number of gaps in time greater than 0.02 seconds in a single, broken (segmented) call.						
Steps (#)	Number of frequency gaps and these steps have no gap in time.						
Pulse Repetition Rate (/s)	Number of pulses per second. Measured using harmonic interval for pulsed and combined calls.						
SNR Qual	<p>Calls rated from 1 (excellent) to 3 (average). Only calls above 10 dB signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) are taken for analysis.</p> <table style="margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto;"> <tr> <td>1 = very high SNR</td> <td>SNR NIST Quick = 20 +</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2 = high SNR</td> <td>SNR NIST Quick = 15 – 20</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3 = moderate SNR</td> <td>SNR NIST Quick = 10 – 15</td> </tr> </table>	1 = very high SNR	SNR NIST Quick = 20 +	2 = high SNR	SNR NIST Quick = 15 – 20	3 = moderate SNR	SNR NIST Quick = 10 – 15
1 = very high SNR	SNR NIST Quick = 20 +						
2 = high SNR	SNR NIST Quick = 15 – 20						
3 = moderate SNR	SNR NIST Quick = 10 – 15						
Classification							
Flat whistle (flatws), mostly flat whistle (flatws.m), ascending whistle (aws) or descending whistle (dws)	<p>To determine whether a whistle was flat, mostly, or had a slope, the bandwidths of the call types listed in Figure 2 of Garland, Castellote and Berchok (2015) were used as guidelines.</p> <table style="margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto;"> <tr> <td>Bandwidth > 136 Hz</td> <td>sloped call (aws or dws)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>93 – 136 Hz</td> <td>mostly flat whistle (flatws.m)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>58 – 92 Hz</td> <td>flat whistle (flatws)</td> </tr> </table>	Bandwidth > 136 Hz	sloped call (aws or dws)	93 – 136 Hz	mostly flat whistle (flatws.m)	58 – 92 Hz	flat whistle (flatws)
Bandwidth > 136 Hz	sloped call (aws or dws)						
93 – 136 Hz	mostly flat whistle (flatws.m)						
58 – 92 Hz	flat whistle (flatws)						

Pulsed and noisy calls	In the selection box, the entire broadband signal was isolated. To determine if the pulsed or noisy call had a slope, a selection box was temporarily placed over the loudest frequency contour of the harmonic sound to see whether the call's bandwidth was greater than a mostly flat whistle (i.e., > 136 kHz). If so, then the pulsed call was determined to have an ascending or descending contour and frequency measurements were recorded from the loudest frequency contour of the harmonic sound. If there was no slope to the call, the start and end frequencies were recorded as peak frequency.
Separate calls	Calls were considered separate and boxed individually if the calls were separated by more than 0.2 seconds.
New call type	To declare a new whistle or pulsed call type, the call needed to be observed at least three times.
Clean call	Call was required to be the only sound in the selection box.
Terminal tail	A call with a final slope (i.e., tail), in a singular direction after a previous change in slope, measuring as fifty percent or more of the call's structure. Calls with a terminal tail were denoted with a "terminal tail" comment. This rule was not applied to flat whistle or mostly flat whistle call types.
Low, Medium or High Category	<p>High = 4+ kHz Medium = 2 – 4kHz Low = 0 – 2 kHz</p> <p>If more than 50% of the call is in one category (i.e., examining the selection box), then the call is labeled as such. If there is an even split between categories, then the peak frequency was used to determine whether the call was categorized as low, medium, or high. These categorizations were not specifically used in this analysis, but categorized as a step for future comparisons.</p>

Figure A. Example spectrograms of whistle types from the eastern Chukchi Sea beluga population sorted by contour category. Mooring noise is also present in a number of the spectrograms. Spectrograms are 1024 point fast Fourier transform (FFT), 23 Hz resolution, Hanning window, and 75% overlap, generated in Raven Pro 1.6.5.

Figure B. Example spectrograms of pulse type A, pulse type R, and noisy calls from the eastern Chukchi Sea beluga population. In the pulse type A calls, note the addition of two contours: n-shaped (pulse.A.n) and u-shaped (pulse.A.u). Spectrograms are 1024 point FFT, 23 Hz resolution, Hanning window, and 75% overlap, generated in Raven Pro 1.6.5.

Figure C. Example spectrograms of pulse type I calls from the eastern Chukchi Sea beluga population. Note the addition of n-shaped (pulse.I.n), u-shaped (pulse.I.u) and segmented pulse type I calls (pulse.I.seg). Spectrograms are 1024 point FFT, 23 Hz resolution, Hanning window, and 75% overlap, generated in Raven Pro 1.6.5.

Figure D. Example spectrograms of combined call types from the eastern Chukchi Sea beluga population. Combined calls have a whistle and pulsed component. The black arrows indicate where the pulsed component is in each combined call. An asterisk in the name denotes combined call types that were not observed more than three times (i.e., did not meet the repetition protocol requirement). Following Brewer et al. (2023), these combined calls are still noted here for future studies. Spectrograms are 1024 point FFT, 23 Hz resolution, Hanning window, and 75% overlap, generated in Raven Pro 1.6.5.

ECS beluga vocal repertoire Random Forest Model:

Table C. Mean decrease in Gini Index values for each variable, averaged across all iterations of the three-fold cross-validation, reflects how the important the variable was in building the Random Forest (RF) Model with higher values corresponding to a higher importance.

Variables of Importance	
	Average Gini Index Value
Number of Inflection Points	21.70
Bandwidth (Hz)	20.67
Frequency Trend (Hz)	16.68
Duration (s)	15.91
Frequency Range (Hz)	13.54
End Frequency (Hz)	9.44
Maximum Frequency (Hz)	9.37
Number of Breaks	9.14
Minimum Frequency (Hz)	9.06
Number of Steps	9.06
Start Frequency (Hz)	9.03
Peak Frequency (Hz)	7.94
Pulse Repetition Rate	6.76

Population Random Forest Model:

Table D. Mean decrease in Gini Index values for each variable, averaged across all iterations of the three-fold cross-validation, reflects how the important the variable was in building the Population Random Forest (RF) Model with higher values corresponding to a higher importance.

Variables of Importance	
	Average Gini Index Value
Frequency Trend (Hz)	72.37
Duration (s)	62.81
Bandwidth (Hz)	56.23
Start Frequency (Hz)	47.84
End Frequency (Hz)	47.67
Frequency Range (Hz)	44.54
Maximum Frequency (Hz)	43.16
Minimum Frequency (Hz)	40.94
Peak Frequency (Hz)	39.43
Number of Inflection Points	21.46
Number of Breaks	14.65
Pulse Repetition Rate	9.68

Whistle-based Population Random Forest Model:

Table E. Mean decrease in Gini Index values for each variable, averaged across all iterations of the three-fold cross-validation, reflects how the important the variable was in building the Whistle-based Population Random Forest (RF) Model with higher values corresponding to a higher importance.

Variables of Importance	
	Average Gini Index Value
Frequency Trend (Hz)	68.76
Duration (s)	58.89
Bandwidth (Hz)	55.50
Start Frequency (Hz)	44.54
Frequency Range (Hz)	42.01
End Frequency (Hz)	39.71
Maximum Frequency (Hz)	37.44
Minimum Frequency (Hz)	36.02
Peak Frequency (Hz)	33.17
Number of Inflection Points	20.28
Number of Breaks	15.11

Table F. Descriptive statistics of variables involved in determining frequency trend (mean \pm standard deviation) for whistles shared by the eastern Chukchi Sea and eastern Beaufort Sea beluga populations, arranged according to contour type. See Appendix 1, Table A for full name descriptions of the call types listed in the first column.

Call Type	Eastern Chukchi Sea Population			Eastern Beaufort Sea Population		
	Frequency (Hz)			Frequency (Hz)		
	Start	End	Frequency Trend (ratio)	Start	End	Frequency Trend (ratio)
ahq	3719 \pm 1179	3775 \pm 1209	0.99 \pm 0.01	2268 \pm 750	3136 \pm 1417	0.76 \pm 0.15
aws	2090 \pm 892	2462 \pm 916	0.84 \pm 0.16	1683 \pm 1017	2219 \pm 982	0.72 \pm 0.18
aws.seg	1529 \pm 642	2068 \pm 646	0.74 \pm 0.19	2262 \pm 685	3361 \pm 1078	0.81 \pm 0.11
rws	1788 \pm 698	1988 \pm 737	0.90 \pm 0.07	2038 \pm 1323	2564 \pm 1470	0.80 \pm 0.15
rws.seg	3581 \pm 1656	3743 \pm 1691	0.95 \pm 0.01	1973 \pm 951	2532 \pm 905	0.77 \pm 0.17
dhq	2449 \pm 1457	2379 \pm 1485	1.05 \pm 0.05	3014 \pm 1151	2739 \pm 1194	1.13 \pm 0.13
dws	2873 \pm 1497	2635 \pm 1504	1.13 \pm 0.15	3169 \pm 1572	2633 \pm 1609	1.40 \pm 0.79
dws.seg	2784 \pm 1201	2305 \pm 1242	1.26 \pm 0.21	3230 \pm 1215	2324 \pm 1300	1.53 \pm 0.37
flatws	2420 \pm 1295	2420 \pm 1296	1.00 \pm 0.01	3012 \pm 1511	3010 \pm 1510	1.00 \pm 0.00
flatws.m	2397 \pm 1398	2396 \pm 1393	1.00 \pm 0.02	3101 \pm 1620	3088 \pm 1617	1.01 \pm 0.04
flatws.seg	2457 \pm 845	2448 \pm 834	1.00 \pm 0.02	3265 \pm 1586	3280 \pm 1572	0.99 \pm 0.03
hq	3698 \pm 1818	3698 \pm 1818	1.00 \pm 0.00	3190 \pm 1236	3191 \pm 1240	1.00 \pm 0.01
modws	2390 \pm 750	2391 \pm 770	1.01 \pm 0.09	2869 \pm 1736	2794 \pm 1763	1.08 \pm 0.31
modws.m	1633 \pm 148	813 \pm 221	2.12 \pm 0.62	2978 \pm 1659	2922 \pm 1554	1.02 \pm 0.26
modws.S	2557 \pm 1552	2471 \pm 1534	1.04 \pm 0.20	2552 \pm 1535	2456 \pm 1269	1.01 \pm 0.26
modws.seg	2336 \pm 1742	2111 \pm 1818	1.23 \pm 0.34	2603 \pm 1470	2571 \pm 1393	1.03 \pm 0.33
nws	2516 \pm 1637	2522 \pm 1636	1.00 \pm 0.08	2554 \pm 1484	2711 \pm 1357	0.92 \pm 0.20
nws.seg.b	1953 \pm 850	1894 \pm 945	1.08 \pm 0.16	3017 \pm 1528	2754 \pm 1419	1.11 \pm 0.18
nws.seg.c	2350 \pm 1292	2271 \pm 1262	1.05 \pm 0.13	2677 \pm 1373	2641 \pm 1486	1.07 \pm 0.38
trill	4113 \pm 2092	4107 \pm 2095	1.00 \pm 0.02	2611 \pm 1733	2674 \pm 1657	0.97 \pm 0.10
uws	2648 \pm 1052	2673 \pm 1085	1.00 \pm 0.11	2670 \pm 1235	2588 \pm 1108	1.03 \pm 0.17
uws.seg.b	3027 \pm 281	2982 \pm 319	1.02 \pm 0.07	2110 \pm 718	2269 \pm 458	0.91 \pm 0.15
uws.seg.c	3793 \pm 2023	3751 \pm 2067	1.02 \pm 0.10	4328 \pm 293	4274 \pm 566	1.02 \pm 0.07
uws.seg.d	4247 \pm 3470	2969 \pm 1389	1.30 \pm 0.56	1370	1602	0.86

Appendix 2:

Discovery Curve

R-code:

```
#####  
# Create a for-loop which goes through 200 different seeds (i.e., 200 different random #  
# shuffles) and plots their different Discovery Curves of the ECS Beluga Vocal Repertoire #  
# on one graph. Then have the average of all iterations plotted as one black line on top of #  
# each iteration. #  
#####  
  
# Install needed packages for a range of colors to display the different iterations of the loop  
install.packages("viridis")  
  
# Activate package  
library(viridis)  
  
# For reproducibility, these are the 200 seeds (i.e., randomized re-ordering) that will be used  
below:  
seeds <- 221 + 1:200  
  
# Create a matrix to keep track of the results of each seed's cumulative tally (i.e., values  
creating the plotted curve)  
seed_cumulative_tally <- matrix(0, nrow=751, ncol=length(seeds))  
  # nrow is my sample size and ncol is the length of the amount of seeds, making  
  # the code easier to adapt if I change the seed count  
  
# Create a for-loop which will randomly re-order the data 200 times, creating 200 different  
Discovery curves and plotting them all on the same graph  
  
for (i in seq_along(seeds)) {  
  set.seed(seeds[i]) # Set a different seed for each loop  
  
  # Randomize the order of the rows (i.e., calls) and create a new data frame  
  ECS_master_list_randomized <-  
ECS_master_list_filtered_100perday[sample(nrow(ECS_master_list_filtered_100perday)), ]  
  
  # Add a new column to the data frame with values of zero  
  ECS_master_list_randomized$Cumulative.Count.of.Qual.Name.Categories <- 0  
  
  # Reorder the columns so that 'Cumulative.Count.of.Qual.Name.Categories' is next to  
'Qual.Name.Clean' column  
  ECS_master_list_randomized[, c("Call.ID", "Duration.s", "Min.Freq.Hz",  
    "Max.Freq.Hz", "Freq.Range.Hz", "Bandwidth.Hz", "Peak.Freq.Hz",  
    "SNR.NIST.Quick.dB", "SNR.Qual", "Start.Freq.Hz", "End.Freq.Hz",  
    "Freq.Trend.Hz", "Num.of.Inflection.Points", "Num.of.Breaks", "Num.of.Steps",  
    "PulseRepRate", "Sequence", "Type", "Qual.Name",
```

```

"Qual.Name.Clean","Cumulative.Count.of.Qual.Name.Categories","Cook.Inlet",
"Comments"]

# Starts the cumulative tally of categories for 'Qual.Name.Clean'
tally_QualNameClean <- 0

# Created to keep track of the unique categories encountered in the if statement below
unique_categories <- integer()

# First line in this nested for loop: each iteration goes through 1 to the amount of rows in
the data frame
for (k in 1:nrow(ECS_master_list_randomized)) {
  # Next: if the category is not N/A in the 'Qual.Name.Clean' column and has not
  #     been seen before in the unique_categories vector then...
  if (!is.na(ECS_master_list_randomized$Qual.Name.Clean[k]) &&
      !(ECS_master_list_randomized$Qual.Name.Clean[k] %in% unique_categories)) {
    # Next: add the unique category to the existing count by combining the value the
    #     existing unique_categories and new category value of the
    #     'Qual.Name.Clean' column at position [k] in the data frame
    unique_categories <- c(unique_categories,
                           ECS_master_list_randomized$Qual.Name.Clean[k])
    # Next line: increase the cumulative tally by 1
    tally_QualNameClean <- tally_QualNameClean + 1
  }
  # Next line: assign the cumulative count to the column that is already created
  ECS_master_list_randomized$Cumulative.Count.of.Qual.Name.Categories[k] <-
  tally_QualNameClean
}

# Create a column with numbers associated to each row as a count of the 'Number of
Calls'
ECS_master_list_randomized$Num.of.Calls <- 1:nrow(ECS_master_list_randomized)

# Place this seed's cumulative tally into the seed_cumulative_tally matrix
seed_cumulative_tally[,i] <-
ECS_master_list_randomized$Cumulative.Count.of.Qual.Name.Categories

# Plot the line of 'Num.of.Calls' against 'Cumulative.Count.of.Qual.Name.Categories' on
the existing plot
lines(ECS_master_list_randomized$Num.of.Calls,
      ECS_master_list_randomized$Cumulative.Count.of.Qual.Name.Categories, col =
viridis(length(seeds))[i], lwd = 2)
}

# Average the cumulative tally across each row for all iterations
avg_seed_cumulative_tally<- rowMeans(seed_cumulative_tally)

# Plot the averaged cumulative tally of all the seeds iterations on top of the other iterations
lines(1:751, avg_seed_cumulative_tally, col="black", lwd=4, lty

```

In each iteration, using a different seed, the data frame of ‘ECS_master_list_filtered_100perday’ (i.e., the original data frame filtered to include only the first 100 calls in each day, according to the methodology) is randomized, creating ‘ECS_master_list_randomized’ data frame. The ‘Qual.Name.Clean’ column shows the corresponding call type for each row in the data frame. This column is designated as “Clean” because the notation indicating whether it was considered high, medium, or low frequency (e.g., L.flatws) was removed from the call type name (e.g., flatws), allowing for the grouping of each call type. The ‘Cumulative.Count.of.Qual.Name.Categories’ column created a tally that increased as each new call type was added, and it was placed next to the ‘Qual.Name.Clean’ column for easier viewing purposes. This column is then plotted against the sample size (i.e., ‘Num.of.Calls’ column) to create the discovery curve.

Random Forest Analysis

The RF Model, Population RF Model, and Whistle-based Population RF Model were generated with the same R-code to create their respective Random Forest three-fold cross-validation. Differences between the models were modifications made when setting up the data prior to the implementation of the for-loop.

R-code for setting up Random Forest (RF) Model data:

```
#####
# Create a balanced training data set                                     #
#####

# Install needed packages
install.packages("dplyr") #helps to manipulate my data

# Activate packages
library("dplyr")

# Set the seed: 222
set.seed(222)

# Create a balanced data set of 15 in each category that qualifies.
df_balanced <- df_filteredcalltype %>%
  group_by(Qual.Name.Clean) %>% # the category I want to group by
  filter(row_number() <= 15) %>% # the amount from each category that
  # I want in my df_balanced
  ungroup()
```

```

# Confirm the variable that I will be using as my outcome variable in the Random Forest
Analysis is a factor.
class(df_balanced$Qual.Name.Clean)    # answer = character

# Convert the outcome variable of 'Qual.Name.Clean' to a factor.
# This next step will take my character variable which is comprised of a sequence of
individual letters and store it as levels (needed for a Random Forest analysis)
df_balanced$Qual.Name.Clean <- as.factor(df_balanced$Qual.Name.Clean)

# Add a column where it numbers 1 - 15 per call type in 'Qual.Name.Clean'.
df_balanced <- df_balanced %>%
  group_by(Qual.Name.Clean) %>%           # the category I want to group by
  mutate(Qual.Name.Clean.Count = row_number()) %>% # mutate creates a new column
                                                    # and row_number assigns
                                                    # numbers for each row according
                                                    # to the category I want to group by
  ungroup()

# Ensure df_balanced is a data frame
df_balanced <- as.data.frame(df_balanced)

```

Both the Population RF Model and the Whistle-based Population RF Model are set up prior to the Random Forest for-loop in the same manner. The main difference is that for the Whistle-based Population RF Model, the data frame was subsetting to include only whistles and the 'Pulse Repetition Rate' column was removed. An equal number of calls from both populations (i.e., 750 for the Population RF Model and 678 for the Whistle-based Population RF Model) were merged to create a new data frame prior to creating the three groups.

R-code for creating the three groups needed for the Random Forest for-loop to implement the three-fold cross-validation:

```

# This code is specific to the creation of Random Forest Model
#####
# Create 3 groups from the balanced data set #
#####

# Add a column where it numbers 1 - 15 per call type in 'Qual.Name.Clean'.
df_balanced <- df_balanced %>%
  group_by(Qual.Name.Clean) %>%           # the category I want to group by
  mutate(Qual.Name.Clean.Count = row_number()) %>% # mutate creates a new column
                                                    # and row_number assigns numbers for each row
                                                    # according to the category I want to group by
  ungroup()

```

```

# Ensure df_balanced is a data frame
df_balanced <- as.data.frame(df_balanced)

# Balanced Group 1: Create a data frame filtering for rows numbered 1-5 from each category
df_balanced_1 <- df_balanced %>%
  filter(Qual.Name.Clean.Count %in% 1:5) %>%
  select(-Qual.Name.Clean.Count)           # drops the new Qual.Name.Clean.Count
                                           # column from the df

# Balanced Group 2: Create a data frame filtering for rows numbered 6-10 from each
category
df_balanced_2 <- df_balanced %>%
  filter(Qual.Name.Clean.Count %in% 6:10) %>%
  select(-Qual.Name.Clean.Count)           # drops the new Qual.Name.Clean.Count
                                           # column from the df

# Balanced Group 3: Create a data frame filtering for rows numbered 11-15 from each
category
df_balanced_3 <- df_balanced %>%
  filter(Qual.Name.Clean.Count %in% 11:15) %>%
  select(-Qual.Name.Clean.Count)           # drops the new Qual.Name.Clean.Count
                                           # column from the df

```

Table G. Model-specific modifications to the R-code for the three separate groups needed for the Random Forest three-fold cross-validation. The ‘Qual.Name.Clean.Count’ column numbers 1 to 15 per call type. The ‘Population.Count’ column is created using the same code, numbering 1 to the total number of calls in each population used in the respective model.

	RF Model	Population RF Model	Whistle-based Population RF Model
Balanced Group 1	1 - 5	1 - 250	1 - 266
Balanced Group 2	6 - 10	251 - 500	227 - 452
Balanced Group 3	11 - 15	501 - 750	453 - 678
Grouping variable	Qual.Name.Clean.Count	Population.Count	Population.Count

R-code used to create the Random Forest for-loop for three-fold cross-validation:

```
#####  
# Create a loop where 2 out of 3 groups are used to train the data and 1 group is used to #  
# test the data. Then repeat with 3 different iterations so that each 1/3 of the data has been #  
# rotated through and used in a Random Forest on both the training and testing data side #  
#####  
  
# Install needed packages for randomForest analysis  
install.packages("randomForest")  
  
# Activate packages  
library("randomForest")  
  
# Create a list of the 3 balanced groups so each group can be accessed by an index value  
df_balanced_groups <- list(df_balanced_1, df_balanced_2, df_balanced_3)  
  
# Initialize a list to store results  
RF_results <- vector("list", length(df_balanced_groups))  
  
# Loop through each balanced data frame group  
for (i in seq_along(df_balanced_groups)) {  
  
  # Create test and training data sets  
  # Test data set is only 1 out of 3 groups, so therefore it is just referenced as i  
  df_test <- df_balanced_groups[[i]]  
  
  # Training data set is every other group besides the test data set  
  df_training <- df_balanced_groups[-i]  
  
  # Combine training data sets if more than one  
  if (length(df_training) > 1) {  
    df_training <- do.call(rbind, df_training) # bind rows in df_training  
  }  
  
  # Train the Random Forest classifier  
  RF_classifier <- randomForest(Qual.Name.Clean ~., data = df_training, ntree=10000)  
  
  # Make predictions on the test data set  
  Test_predictions <- predict(RF_classifier, newdata = df_test)  
  
  # Calculate the confusion matrix  
  confusion_matrix <- table(Test_predictions, df_test$Qual.Name.Clean)  
  
  print(paste("Variable Importance Plot", i))  
  varImpPlot((RF_classifier))  
  
  Variable_Importance_GI_Values <- importance(RF_classifier)  
  paste("Variable Importance Gini Index Values", i)
```

```
# Store results in RF_results list
RF_results[[i]] <- list(model = RF_classifier, confusion_matrix = confusion_matrix,
  Variable_Importance_GI_Values = Variable_Importance_GI_Values)
}

RF_results
```